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Middle East Institute for Higher Education School-University Partnership: Process, Structure, Outcomes, and Impact

**The Middle East Institute for Higher
Education at The American University
in Cairo**

School-University Partnership: Process, Structure, Outcomes and Impact

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Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Partners Acronyms

AUC	American University in Cairo
ANSU	Ain Shams University
AU	Alexandria University
HU	Helwan University
ULEIC	University of Leicester
UON	University of Northampton
UL	University of Limerick
MLU	Martin-Luther University

Other Acronyms and Abbreviations

SUP4PCL	School and University Partnership for Peer Communities of Learners
ACBEU	Admission Co-ordination Bureau of Egyptian Universities
ARAS	Action Research for All Schools (project coordinated by the Middle East institute for Higher Education)
BERA	British Educational Research Association
CAI	Computer Assisted Instruction
CAPMAS	Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics

CDC	Curriculum Development Committee
CPD	Continuous Professional Development
EKB	Egyptian Knowledge Bank
ESD	Education for Sustainable Development
ETCP	Egyptian Technical Colleges Project
FOE	Faculties of Education
FGD	Focus Group Discussion
FLDP	Faculty-Leadership Development Project
GC	Global Citizenship
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HEEPF	Higher Education Enhancement Project Fund
IAI	Internet Assisted Instruction
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ICTP	Information and Communication Technology Project
ID	Identification

IRB	Institutional Research Board
INSET	In-service education of teachers
KG	Kindergarten
MEIHE	Middle East Institute for Higher Education
MENA	Middle East and North Africa
MOETE	Ministry of Education and Technical Education
MOHE	Ministry of Higher Education
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
NCATE	National Council for Accrediting Teacher Education
NCED	National Centre of Curricula Development
NCEEE	National Centre for Examinations and Educational Evaluation
NCER	National Centre for Education Research
OECD	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PCL	Peer Communities of Learners
PAT	Professional Academy for Teachers
PDS	Professional Development Schools

PD	Professional Development
PI	Principle Investigator
QAAP	Quality Assurance and Accreditation Project
QAU	Quality Assurance Unit
SEN	Special Education Needs
SCU	Supreme Council of Universities
STEAM	Science, Technology, Art, Engineering and Mathematics
SU	School-University
UNICEF	United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
USAID	United States Agency for International Development

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Preface

The partnership is the result of an Erasmus+ project that was awarded to the Middle East Institute for Higher Education at the Graduate School of Education in the American University in Cairo entitled School-University Partnership for Peer Communities of Learners (SUP4PCL) in November 2016. The partnership was created within a context where Egypt has shown a keen need for reform at the school and university levels and where Faculties of Education have acquired the reputation of operating in an ivory tower divorced from the practical field of school improvement. A continued debate has called for the abolition of faculties and schools of education at the undergraduate level and the relegation of their work to the graduate level; hence, the eternal struggle between sequential and concurrent teacher education programs. The partnership was therefore viewed by Egypt's Supreme Council of Universities and Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research as a welcome step in the direction of creating cost-effective means of stimulating a reform environment. For several decades, the international reform community has recognized the importance of school-university partnerships and the creation of Professional Development Schools (PDS) in offering an effective method of creating collaboration, continuous professional development, research, and pedagogical innovation. The proponents of this approach have claimed that it can simultaneously reform school practices and teacher education programs. It is the intention of the SUP4PCL consortium in Egypt to introduce such an approach with the support and creation of Peer Communities of learners (PCLs) at the university, school, and cross-cultural levels.

Due to some bureaucratic delays, it is only in late February of 2017 that the partnership was enacted with the first Kick-off meeting of the project. During this initial first phase, partnership teams were being constructed within the eight institutions of the consortium; Ain Shams University ANSU, Helwan University HU, Alexandria University AU (from Egypt), University of Limerick UL, (from Ireland) Martin Luther University (from Germany), University of Northampton UON, University of Leicester ULEIC (from UK), and the American University in Cairo AUC, coordinating the consortium from Egypt. Moreover, the various institutions with very diverse cultural and political backgrounds were beginning to know each other. The early stages of consolidating this layer of the partnership were animated with meetings and much mobility to learn about each other in live natural environments. During this preparatory preliminary phase, another layer was added to the partnership namely that between Egyptian Faculties of Education and Professional Development Schools (PDSs). The first step in that direction was a signed Memorandum of Understanding MOU between the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research and the Ministry of Education and Technical Education. Under this protocol, three faculties were to partner with a total of 15 public governmental schools at a ratio of 5 to each faculty later to expand to a total of 45 schools at a ratio of 15 schools per faculty. The MOU was followed by signed letters of agreement with the Ministry of Education local directorates. After some months, more closeness was established between the partners through exchange visits, activities, communication and meetings in the summer of 2018. Halfway through the project, another dimension to the partnership was added, namely a twinning process was introduced with the following arrangement: AUC twinning with ULEIC for quality assurance and monitoring purposes, AU with UON twinning for capacity development and the write up of case studies, similarly for the same purposes HU twinned with MLU and ANSU with UL. Finally, in 2019 yet another dimension was added to the partnership with the clustering of PDSs thus allowing for these to expand to 45 with a ratio of 15 per each Faculty of Education (FOE). The various case studies of this project will cover all the layers and dimensions of the enhanced and expanding partnership.

All the participants in the expanding partnership/consortium reached consensus on a research framework with set questions shaping the work of each of the case studies. Together, the various case studies constitute a level of triangulation that supports and assures the integrity of interpretation especially that the collection of data was done at different points in time by different research teams in similar settings. The total data generated from this project has the potential of being utilized for grounded theory and to further refine concepts and comparative approaches to school-university partnerships, and Peer Communities of Learners PCL.

Malak Zaalouk

Introduction

“School-University Partnership is not a project: It is a way of life”

(Burton & Greher, 2007, p.15)

However

“A partnership that has as its purpose the creation of a partnership-rather the accomplishment of some ultimate goal- is inevitably doomed to early failure”

(Clark, 1999, p.168)

This case study will examine the process of building the partnership, the shape, nature and structure it took and finally what can we consider to be the major outputs of the partnership to date. Before we go into each of these three components, process, structure and outcomes, it is worth mentioning initially that this partnership is an *enhanced partnership* that is complex, multi-dimensional, multi-layered, expanding and flexible. The study will at times touch upon the *enhanced* nature of the partnership especially when touching upon the impact of the European partners as perceived by faculty members and teachers as well as the role of local administrators, communities, and parents.

The partnership in the SUP4PCL project adopted the Professional Development School model. Goodlad (1993) defines the Professional Development schools as a partnership that acts as a “centre of inquiry in which individuals – from both sets of institutions- study presumably to improve teaching, learning and perhaps teacher education” (p.25). More specific definitions around Professional Development Schools (PDS) suggest that the “PDS is an undertaking of schools and schools of education to create places in which entering teachers can combine theory and practice in a setting organized to support their learning; veteran teachers can renew their own professional development and assume new roles as mentors, university adjuncts, and teacher leaders, and school and university educators can together engage in research and rethinking of practice...Ideally the university program and the school develop a shared conception of good teaching that informs their joint work” (Darling-Hammond, 2005, p.vii).

The PDS movement that emerged in the USA defined its mission in four dimensions namely; the preparation

of new teachers, university faculty development, inquiry directed at the improvement of practice and last but not least, enhanced student achievement. This fourfold mission-inspired our SUP4PCL initiative in Egypt. It was also inspired by some of the levels developed by the Holmes group, which led the movement in the USA and with the help of the National Council for Accrediting Teacher Education NCATE developed standards in 2001 as a guideline for Professional Development Schools. We found these guidelines very useful for our work as they trace the journey through four levels. A first level which simply looks at the beginning stage of planning and committing to the development of a PDS. A second level which they called a developing level wherein the partners pursued and developed the mission of PDS even though no policy was put in place. A third level, they called performing at standard wherein policies were put in place and the PDS partnership became part of the two institutions while they closely collaborate, work closely together and cooperation has become the norm. A last and fourth level is called the leading level and it alludes to the partnership being very advanced, sustainable and generative (Arnold, 2015).

While other case studies in the project will be more focused on the formation of Peer Communities of Learners (PCLs), the focus of this research is on the nature of the partnership between schools and universities under the Erasmus+ funded project and its impact. This particular case study will be concerned with the partnership between the three Egyptian Faculties of Education and the 15 Professional Development Schools (PDS) out of which two of the schools dropped out. The major protagonists of this section are faculty from the three universities, along with teachers and school principals from the 13 schools. The study aims to answer the following main research questions:

RQ1 What is the nature of the partnership in the project?

RQ2 How does the School-University Partnership SUP impact on practices, beliefs, values, and attitudes?

RQ3 What are some of the tensions between beliefs, values, and practices?

Context

This section looks at the context found in the schools and faculties of education (FOE) at the beginning of the SUP4PCL project. The first part of this section starts with the status of education in Egypt and local contextual issues in FOEs and Egyptian schools. The second part of this section describes the FOEs and schools and provides information related to the demographics of those involved in the project. The third part of this section describes the various interventions and activities implemented throughout the lifetime of the project

Figure 1. Outline of SUP4PCL context

Section 1

Status of education in Egypt

The Egyptian educational system is well known for its centralised operations that continue to emulate the French bureaucratic model adopted by the Ottoman ruler Mohamed Ali (Ibrahim, 2010). It is also known to be the largest educational system in MENA and Africa with more than 18 million students (USAID, 2018). The actual expenditure on pre-university education did not exceed 3% of the GDP in 2013 while in 2016 it reached 4% (Oxford Business Group, 2019). The Egyptian Ministry of Education (MOETE) develops national policies, legislations, and standards. It also has a main role in monitoring and evaluating policy implementation. Curricula are developed through the MOETE and human resources are managed there too by incentives. Three centres support the efforts of the MOETE. These are the National Centre of Curricula

Development (NCED), National Centre for Education Research (NCER) and the National Centre for Examinations and Educational Evaluation (NCEEE).

The educational system has been facing serious challenges and has been through various reform efforts trying to provide a facelift to the current status. Several national strategic plans were introduced such as the 2002 - 2007; 2007 - 2012 and recently the 2012-2017 national strategic plan. The focus of these reforms was decentralization, quality, school-based reform, accountability, accreditation, and wider community participation (MOE, 2007). The main achievements of these national strategies is the reduction of attrition rates in addition to efforts that increase professionalism of teachers' work and autonomy of school principals (OECD, 2015). The MOETE proposed a national strategic plan for pre-university education reform 2014-2030. The goals of this strategic plan are to improve the quality of education through: school-based reform, professional development and human resources, development of curricula, support the use of technology in schools, and monitoring and evaluation. Through a World Bank loan, Education 2.0 is the new wave to education in Egypt (MOE, 2019; Shohdy, 2016). A new wave to education was deemed necessary by the government as according to a 2017-2018 report by the World Economic Forum, Egypt ranked 129th globally in terms of the quality of education (Schwab, 2019). An earlier 2013 USAID report similarly revealed that "one in five students in Egypt in grade three could not read a single word from a reading passage, 50 percent of students with five years of schooling were functionally illiterate, and only 67 percent could do basic mathematics" (USAID, 2013, p.3). UNICEF's study also commented on the persistence of finding traditional teaching methods in Egypt stating that an Egyptian child is far more likely to be taught using traditional 'chalk and talk' methods (Al-Ashkar, 2018).

As for the status of teachers, by looking back into the history of education in Egypt, a noticeable decline in the status of teachers started from 1962. At that time, there was a need to educate more and more students who were enrolling in the free educational system announced by Gamal Abdel Nasser, Egypt's former President 1956-1970. This demand required massive hiring where some were not qualified and school facilities

were scarce. This led to the decline of teachers' social status and schools to operate in double shifts (Barsoum, 2004). With the extension of compulsory education to nine years instead of six under Mubarak's presidency in the 1980s, more and more students entered high school and universities leading to more graduates than what the labour market could absorb.

With reference to how education in Egypt is managed, the MOETE is supported by Muddiriyas and Idaras. The former performs mainly organisational, analytical and monitoring tasks, such as compiling comprehensive situation analyses of the districts' performance. For that to take place, it uses standards determined by the MOETE. It also provides technical support to the districts, developing the educational plans at the governorate level, co-ordinating the decentralisation of the curriculum, managing the printing and distribution of books, and maintenance of the educational buildings with the Idaras. The Idaras are responsible for developing an annual report on the state of education in the governorate which registers and analyses the variables and learning outcomes in light of the districts' reports. Idaras also provide training programmes and are responsible for the development of final year primary and preparatory stage examinations. These are based on the directives and blueprints developed by the MOETE through the work of the National Centre for Examination and Educational Evaluation (NCEEE) (OECD, 2015).

School context

Quality of teachers and teaching

The teaching profession in Egypt tends to be associated with a low social and economic status (Loveluck, 2012). This notion is reinforced by the low salaries and poor-quality of professional development (El-Khouly, 2018). Teaching in schools is mainly dominated by teacher-led instructions over student-centered ones. This seems to be a backlash result of the closed-ended type of assessment that encourages rote learning and a heavy reliance on memorisation. To rectify the status of teachers, similar to the efforts done to improve the educational system by the various reforms, there have been significant efforts to support teachers. The National Standards for Education was established in 2003, in addition to the establishment of the Teachers Cadre in 2007, which paved the way for a career path and promotional system along with a 50% increase

in basic pay. In 2008, the Professional Academy for Teachers (PAT) was established and had as its mandate planning and reviewing standards of continuous teacher professional development (CPD) and promotion, issuing teaching profession certification, accreditation of professional development and all training services providers, and finally supporting educational and pedagogical research and ensuring its application. Brophy and Good (1986) noted that good teachers are the essence of forming good schools, and improving teachers' skills and knowledge through professional development (Guskey, 1995) is one of the most important investments of time and money that local, state, and national leaders make in education.

Despite the various efforts to improve the quality of teachers, according to the World Bank (2010) report, in-service education of teachers (INSET) and CPD in Egypt fit largely into the traditional mode of in-service provision—short one-off courses of lectures, workshops, seminars, and qualification programmes with little or no follow-up similar to that in other Arab countries (EL-Deghaidy, Mansour, & Al-Shamrani, 2015). Teachers tend to perceive CPD offered by the MOETE as repetitive and with no value. The World Bank described it as “wide in content but narrow in sharing good practice throughout the system” (World Bank, 2010, p.9). Throughout this project, teachers seemed to be resistant to attending workshops and meetings thinking that FOE will offer similar sessions as those by the MOETE.

School facilities and density

Due to Egypt's high population, reaching over 99 million (CAPMAS, 2019), schools face a problem of class density. The Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics (CAPMAS) reported that the average number of students per class in the primary stage is 46 students, the preparatory stage 43 students and the general secondary stage 39 students (OECD, 2015) (Figure 2).

The numbers also indicate that Egypt has the highest average class size compared to other countries. It supports the fact that the average class size is almost 80% more than OECD countries (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Average class size across educational stages

Figure 3. Average class size in Egypt compared to other countries.

Sullivan (2012) reported that teachers in larger classes adopted negative interactions with the students due to being overwhelmed. However, Bourke (1986) noted that teachers in smaller classes spent more time monitoring the students and providing them instant feedback.

Another main factor that affects class density is the freeze on teacher hire that impacted the system negatively and led to shortages in some disciplines. To resolve this issue, the MOETE started to hire teachers on a non-permanent contractual system. In 2010, teachers representing this system rose to around 45% (MOE, 2010). Another factor that has an impact on classrooms is the maldistribution of teachers across schools leading to shortages in some subjects versus a large increase in other subjects. There are also shortages in some governorates versus others (Strategic plan 2014-2030, n.d.). Schools are facing problems in regards to reallocating teachers to different schools to cover for teacher shortages in some areas. Figure 4 shows the distribution of teachers and the surpluses according to the educational stages.

Table 5.3 Surpluses and shortages of teachers, aggregated by level of schooling

School level	Aggregated gross surpluses of teachers	Aggregated gross shortages of teachers	Net surplus (+) shortage (-)
Primary	44 736	21 155	+23 581
Preparatory	5 332	22 156	-16 824
Secondary	701	18 296	-17 595
Total	50 769	61 607	+10 838

Source: Statistics supplied by MOE for 2011-12, in Dewidar, A. (2012), *Regional Study on Teacher Policies Phase II: Egypt Case Study*, World Bank, Washington, DC.

Figure 4. Surpluses and shortages of teachers by school level.

Also, it is very much possible to find teachers being promoted to a different school. Moreover, there are schools in Egypt that work using a double shift mode to accommodate the large number of students (Figure 5). Among many problems, overcrowded classrooms is a widespread problem in Egyptian public schools due to the tight budget of the government (Bolbol, Zalal, Hammam, & Elnakeb, 2017). According to the UNICEF (2014) report, the enrolment rate at the primary level has exceeded 90%. This number is stated by the Global Competitiveness Report in 2016 which confirmed that the enrolment rate has reached 98%.

Source: Ministry of Education (MoE)

Figure 5. Percentage of schools functioning on full days' versus double shifts

Recently teachers have been challenged with a new educational system known by Education 2.0. The new system starts from KG-Primary grade 3 and is based on interdisciplinary thematic learning. Teachers are finding it confusing and difficult to handle as their time is limited and resistance to changing to a different system than what they are used to is causing them many discomforts. In one of the project's schools namely the Lilly school, they have another related issue to resistance to change as teachers' age was clearly higher than in other schools involved in the project. This meant that teachers' years of experience was

longer 20-30 years and that changing what they were used to do would seem to be harder. It was clear that some of these teachers did not participate in any recent CPD offered by the MOETE. This made them more willing to learn and eager to engage and participate in the SUP4PCL project.

In terms of infrastructure, schools vary in the facilities they have. While some have computer labs according to the national policy of one laboratory for every 15 classes (Hamdy, 2007), others are not able to have this fulfilled as computer labs are only available in 12% of primary schools, 42% of preparatory schools and 23% of secondary schools, with only half of them connected to the Internet (OECD, 2015). Lack of Internet connectivity and limited availability of computers, in general, seems to limit teachers on integrating computer-assisted instruction (CAI) and internet assisted instruction (IAI) which seem an obvious result. Nonetheless, Mason, Pelgrim, and Plomp (2008) argue that teachers' adoption of ICT and CAI vary widely according to the teachers and not due to the technology availability in schools.

Collegiality in schools

The working conditions of teachers and the implementation of the educational system do not seem to allow for collegial interactions. Teachers as experts in their own discipline might not have much to discuss with teachers of other disciplines. The rough working conditions also hinder quality time for reflection and building connections resulting in teacher burnout. In a study by Badawy (2015), teachers experienced medium to high levels of stress and medium levels of burnout. The research findings suggest that Egyptian teachers report little involvement and supervisors' support, little autonomy, little co-worker cohesion, little innovation and little physical comfort. As for reflective practices, both reflection-in-action and on-action (Schon, 1983) were not documented as daily practices teachers in Egypt and other Arab countries (Al-issa & Al-bulushi, 2010) would apply, unless explicitly directed to do so (Abdou, 2017). Teachers are consumed to cover course content according to timetables set by the MOETE. It is not usual to find teachers visiting others in classes or providing peer feedback. It is very well perceived as a lonely profession (Cacioppo & Patrick, 2008). Baumeister, DeWall, Ciarocco, and Twenge (2005) stressed that social acceptance is one of the

motivations for the development of teachers' ability to self-regulate. When the goal of positive relationships is not achieved, as in many cases of school teachers, and individual experiences rejected, their ability to self-regulate reduces, leading to behaviours that will ultimately reinforce the feelings of loneliness, in a self-destructive cycle (Cacioppo & Patrick, 2008).

As for school principals and leadership positions, it should be noted that school leadership is an important aspect of the educational system. It has been researched extensively as it affects many other factors in the educational process such as students' academic achievement, teachers' performance and teacher retention (Habashy, 2015). The main trend found in the 13 participating schools in the Erasmus project, shows that the majority are more inclined to follow an autocratic style of leadership at different levels, while the minority leaned more towards a mix between autocratic and democratic styles. Such leadership styles can be hindering factors to any proposed change in school. Although the policy discourse in Egypt emphasises that school leaders are autonomous leaders, in reality, schools in Egypt are dominated by those who hinder teachers' professional development and enact practices where teachers are isolated in their classrooms and given limited opportunities to grow professionally (Abdou, 2017). In schools where teachers were either enrolled in Ph.D. programmes or were awarded the degree, school principals were giving them a hard time. According to school visits to one of the schools, the leader of the school was a challenge to the FOE members due to wanting to avoid the influence on teachers by anyone but him. With a traditional mindset, the school principal was not open to change nor to including contemporary practices such as reflection, democratic decision making etc... (Iris school observation report, 2018).

Security and access

For the project team members to implement the planned activities and interventions at FOE and schools, access to these locations were needed. Access to educational institutions in Egypt is a delicate issue and requires going through a lengthy system of approvals and security checks. Non-Egyptians are not allowed to enter schools and are only allowed to higher education institutions if they receive security clearance, that can take over a month. Passport copies and reasons for why

and who they meet are needed before setting foot on campus. The same goes for Egyptians visiting these educational institutions yet the process can be shorter while copies of national IDs are needed and sent in advance with notice at the campus gates. To help gain access and also to start a close partnership through the Erasmus+ project between schools and universities, the project PI established the cornerstone of this project with the signed MoU between the minister of higher education and minister of education and technological education. This was followed by signed agreements between the faculties of education and the relevant Idara in their locality. Signatures at both of these levels required months of follow-up to the degree that one of the FOEs took eight months to get these signatures finalised. From that point on, it was left to each FOE to start extensive discussions with school principals to access each school within its proximity. FOE had problems accessing schools due to either restriction from the school principals or due to the timing of the needed visits. In various instances throughout the lifetime of the project, FOE members could not enter the schools as there were exams which delayed data collected at different points. Grading exam papers is yet another time where access to schools was almost impossible. There were also national elections held at some schools and the entire school was shut down. Some schools allowed the FOE members to enter but would then forbid teachers to leave their classes and stop them from attending the Peer Communities of Learner (PCL) meetings, causing further disruption and delays.

Not only did the school have access problems but also FOEs had issues related to their context and responsibilities around the year. End of semester exams and grading times were also when the FOE members found difficulty to meet for their PCLs or leave their workplaces to visit and mentor school PCL members. In conclusion, access and security issues were the main obstacles in the project. For these same reasons, even parents are prevented to have access to these educational institutions, isolating schools from their communities and preventing the community to provide support when needed. Yet, through the project schools and universities opened their doors to establish partnerships for the very first time and to extend this partnership to other neighbouring schools and even open up to the local community which in itself is a great accomplishment.

Discipline and bullying issues

Issues related to discipline and bullying are not new when referring to schools. What is new, is that it can happen on different levels and by different means. Bullying has different and diverse facets/manifestations. These include bodily, mental assault, use of harsh and rude language, or terrorizing in an attempt to bring about a feeling of fright, anxiety, submission or damage to the bullied (Said, 2018). These actions can be carried out verbally through threatening, taunting, teasing, and/or calling names, or non-verbally through hitting, pushing, kicking, pinching or restraining another by physical contact (Schuster, 1996). Furthermore, it is described as “submission to power as a result of not being in control, in this case, the powerful person assaults the less powerful one” (Sentse, Scholte, & Voeten, 2007, p.1011). A study in North Africa by Abdirahman, Fleming, and Jacobsen, (2013) highlighted the significant prevalence rate of bullying in Egypt compared to other Arab countries. Egypt had twice the amount of bullying reports than those in Libya, Morocco, and Tunisia over a one-month span.

The schools included in this Erasmus project varied in terms of the magnitude each had in terms of discipline and bullying issues. One school of the 13 schools involved in the project had clear bullying issues with their students. In that school, parents of the students were working in high positions in governmental offices around the school. Students were bullying teachers whenever a problem occurred and threatened to tell their parents who would come to school and cause trouble. Students were also bullying each other during break time and in class. The school definitely had a problem with discipline (Lilly school observation, 20th March, 2019).

Status of higher education in Egypt

In Egypt, there are 31 private universities and 26 national universities (Ramage, 2019). The majority of students are enrolled in national universities rather than private universities (Figure 6). Similar to the pre-university educational system, higher education is also centralised. A recent OECD report, *Reviews of National Policies for Education: Higher Education in Egypt 2010*, identified the over-centralization of authority in Egypt’s universities as one of the main obstacles to reform. Recent efforts to reform higher education go

back to 2009 when the Ministry of Higher Education (MOHE) started a major project that included five sub-topics including Quality Assurance and Accreditation Project (QAAP), Higher Education Enhancement Project Fund (HEEPF), Information & Communication Technology Project (ICTP), Faculty-Leadership Development Project (FLDP), Egyptian Technical Colleges Project (ETCP) (World Bank, 2009). QAAP has urged faculties in public universities to ensure that the curricular content meets the expectations of stakeholders for that reason educational programmes can be updated through a curriculum development committee (CDC) established by the Quality Assurance Unit (QAU) in each faculty engaged with QAAP. The CDC committee is chaired by the dean and includes vice-deans, the QA unit manager, and department heads. As for the FLDP, results from studies (i.e., Abdelmotaleb, 2010; Almorsy, 2009; Hussien, 2013) seem to reach to similar conclusions that faculty members did not benefit as expected due to short notice of session announcements, topics not related to their needs, repeated sessions if a faculty member would apply for promotion for the rank of associate and full professor, a disconnect with the content as they were decided top-down.

Figure 6. Enrolment in Higher Education institutions across Egypt

Faculties of Education context

All of the 26 national universities include a faculty of education. The faculties of education (FOE) in Egypt generally aim to educate prospective teachers for the various stages of general education; educate teachers at the postgraduate level; function as a centre for research, through master and doctorate degrees; enhance the professional and academic level of teachers by in-service training; disseminate state-of-the-art pedagogies and ideologies to stakeholders; and exchange experience and information with various cultural and educational

institutions, nationally and internationally. World Bank Faculty of Education Project identified the following weaknesses in FOEs: low or uneven faculty quality, inadequate facilities, weak instructional resources, uneven management, poor quality controls governing entry, out-of-date standards, and lack of incentive for institutions to improve the quality of their teacher education programmes (Dewidar, 2012).

To become a teacher, students enrol in a teacher education four-year programme where they study educational and academic courses depending on their specialty (i.e., biology, Maths, English, Special Education, ...). According to statistics from OECD 2018, 78% of all teachers in Egypt have a bachelor's degree in education whereas 22% have degrees from other schools (MOE, 2010). Entrance to faculties of education, as for other disciplines of study, is determined by students' scores in their secondary school leave certificate (as cited in ELKerdany, 2014). Admission to faculties of Medicine and Engineering, like many other Arab countries, require students to achieve a total percentage in their end of school leaving exam of over 98%. Education requires a more modest total percentage that can start from 75% and above depending on the major. Figure 7 illustrates the top 10 fields of study across different disciplines in national universities.

Figure 7. Top 10 fields of study across national universities.

Due to the university entrance system in Egypt known by Admission Co-ordination Bureau of Egyptian Universities (ACBEU), many students allocated by the central placement office could end up in programmes different to their preferences just because of the final

grade in secondary leave exam *thanawiya amma* or due to having the programme reach its cap. Those ending up at the faculty of education could be part of such students who have little or no interest in education. The result of such practice is that faculties of education are seen as the ‘dumping grounds’ (OECD, 2015, p. 118) for weak students who have nowhere else to go. Such practice results in overcrowded classes in FOEs and halls packed with students, especially in tracks where private tuition is prevailing. Nonetheless, there are cases where students entering FOEs are there by choice. Results from the motivation questionnaire administrated after the first year of the project to teachers participating in the Erasmus+ project showed that the majority had high motivational levels and were satisfied in their profession as school teachers.

Pre-service student teachers in Egypt enrol at FOEs that provide concurrent BSc (Ed) or BA (Ed) programmes, in which student teachers pursue their professional studies while also studying academic subjects in their areas of specialisation. Teacher education programmes are designed around the following main courses that present knowledge and skills in three areas: academic, professional and cultural. They represent 75%, 20% and 5% respectively of the total number of hours of the programme (EL-Deghaidy, 2010; Ibrahim, 2007). Dahawy (2008) presented a review of previous studies that discussed problems found in the academic programmes offered in the previous by-law. Examples of these problems are: the wide variation in the weight of the academic course among divisions; graduates seem to have lower levels of content understanding compared to those from other faculties; some university members from faculties other than Education underestimate students and hold negative attitudes towards them.

In terms of the faculty members, they are appointed on a tenure basis. They are hired based on their merit at the undergraduate level. Unfortunately, these positions are of low salary with poor working conditions and limited faculty office spaces. Faculty are promoted to ranks of associate and full professors based on their research activity, teaching, professional development and service. Research is the main component in their dossiers and represents 70-80% of the total weight. Promotion of faculty members takes place twice a year with little being added to assess their

teaching. Promotion is mainly based on their research publications with minimal grades given to teaching and service activities. Said, a faculty member in the project, stated that most universities do not foster innovative research and the productivity level is less than expected. Faculty mainly publish for the sake of promotion to full professors. Due to limited funding opportunities allocated for research and issues related to the quality of research, there are scarce opportunities for finding research in peer-reviewed international Journals. Another reason for the limited publications in international peer-reviewed journals is the language barrier. Faculties of education offer its programmes and publishes its research and theses throughout Egypt in Arabic except for foreign language departments such as English and French resulting in further limitations at the international level.

To help improve the effectiveness of faculty members at FOEs, Sorcinelli (2002) suggested 10 principles for faculty development. From these 10, is developing faculty ownership in identifying their needs. One way to do that is by having faculty mentors. These mentors could be provided with modest incentives in return for their time and effort supporting another faculty. Another principle relates to encouraging collegiality and community whether from the same or from different disciplines. Two interrelated principles focus on incentives and recognition. Support could be either financial by rewards or administrative support to facilitate and motivate faculty for participation in faculty development. Time and willingness seem the core of the contextual barriers to change. In one of the interviews, the following was stated: “Resistance to change is problematic, we need sessions on how to fight resistance to change ...in Egypt, there is a lot of resistance to change even if the new idea is good just the fear of change and taking risks is very much evident” (Mahmoud, Interview, Feb 24th, 2019). From the various challenges that hinder change are aspects related to the time release. “At FOE, there is no release time to do research work, the load is heavy and you have to teach the courses given to you” (Mohga, Interview, March 4th, 2019).

Teaching at FOEs

Teaching is mainly lecture-based where students have to physically come to campus and attend classes. There is an attendance system in FOEs and students

are deducted grades if they do skip classes. During the lectures the main aim is knowledge transfer with domination of faculty talk time, most probably using a one-way direction and limited interaction. Students in class are seated in rows in a theatre layout where the faculty members take their place at the front of class near the board. The layout limits interaction and movement among students together and with faculty. Also, there are large numbers of students which limits student engagement (Dalal, Interview, Feb 20th, 2019). Such an environment provides scarce opportunities to develop positive relations with students as they are mostly distant from the faculty members. One interviewee mentioned that “when students are silent in class, I now think about it, it could be because they are afraid to speak up their minds” (Elham, Interview, March 18th, 2019).

Teaching in some cases relies on the use of technology. “Most FOEs are equipped with Data shows that are useful for PowerPoint presentations. Such facilities are available in a small number of classes and not all of these are functioning well due to low maintenance and expenses. As for Smartboards, these are available in computer labs, not classes” (Safaa, Interview, Feb 20th, 2019). “Technology is underused and did not seem to be an integral part of teaching” (Mohga, Interview, March 4th, 2019). “Faculty in FOEs are not that free to do as they please. I cannot tell my students let’s go to online learning, we have a system that we have to follow and regulations to abide to” (Doaa, Interview, March 20th, 2019).

Hierarchy and power relations in FOEs

FOEs have a clear hierarchy and power relations are prominent. Faculty are ranked by an academic ranking system where those in the highest level (full-time professors) seem to have the greatest power over the lower ranks. Full-time faculty are voting members and can dominate discussions given their seniority. Such a system allows for authoritative power relations that are neither healthy nor accepting to change easily. Mahmoud (assistant lecturer) mentioned that “it was expected from him to attend classes with his department chair (full-time professor) and sit in these classes to learn as one of the students” (Mahmoud, Interview, Feb 24th, 2019) he accepted due to not being able to reject or question the power of the full-time professor. To emphasize this point further, “in some cases, ideas

are offered by assistant lecturers who are just starting their career trajectories, yet these ideas are not heard nor considered as they are not coming from the top ranks add” (Jamila, Interview, Feb 20th, 2019). Content is also developed by full-time faculty with little input from assistant lecturers.

Moreover, there are hierarchal issues related to the age range of faculty still employed in higher educational institutions. Although the official retirement age is 60, faculty members can still teach but with no administrative responsibility for those over the retirement age. Having faculty not leaving their job positions limits the opportunity for replacing these positions with younger faculty members.

Collaboration in FOEs

The general context of FOEs in Egypt is competitive with negligible attempts to finding collaborative activities among faculty. Not all faculty are motivated to working in innovative settings. Some are so immersed in their own work and have no time to be occupied by additional tasks. Such an individualistic culture is against sharing ideas or engaging in team projects, working in isolated silos is more of the norm. The norm in terms of faculty work is that each have their own courses and come to campus to teach and attend meetings. Most activities that faculty are involved in are done individually with little collaboration within and across departments and schools, let alone across universities. Faculty are praised for publishing individual research that are given higher grades on a point system compared to collaborative research where the grade is reduced to 50% of its weight. Mohga, (Interview, March 4th, 2019), mentioned that it is “very usual to suddenly hear about someone who got promoted. This person was working on their own, which is the norm in academia here in Egypt, although I personally see that engaging in collaborative research enriches the quality as it includes different perspectives and as they say two heads are better than one”. Another factor is limited opportunities to meet and discuss in a collegial manner. “Faculty rarely meet to talk, everyone is occupied by their own work and interests” (Mohga, Interview, March 4th, 2019). Projects that can bring faculty together are not that popular. In one of the faculties of education the Erasmus plus project was their first encounter with international projects and was seen as both a challenge and opportunity.

As for **co-teaching** some faculty supported the idea but were concerned about implementation difficulties due to the strict and rigid system. It is mainly due to the need to have a supportive system that helps manage faculty time and their responsibilities. According to Dalila (Interview, March 4th, 2019), “having a supportive system is key to the success of any innovation as without it you are isolated from the whole context and could be emotionally overwhelmed if you are not appreciated and acknowledged that you are doing something good. The context is individualistic and functions on setting preliminary priorities rather than quality...all of our work (referring to the work done for the project) should be counted as part of our workload and responsibilities. The need for appreciation and job satisfaction is more important than materialistic reward ...many people would be motivated if the context was supportive.”

University to school connection through teacher practicum

Pre-service teachers at the faculties of education (FOE) undergo teacher practicum in schools. Teacher practicum is a fundamental part of the programme that can be considered as the “nurturing ground” (Fung, 2005, p.49) for prospective teachers to develop dispositions toward the profession. This takes place in their third and fourth year of the teacher education programme. The usual scenario is that groups of students attend a full day at a school and interact with students, teachers and administrators while entering classes and teaching students. During a practicum day, pre-service teachers are also involved in all school activities similar to what hired teachers would be doing. To follow up on pre-service teachers’ performances, a university professor from the faculty of education visits the school. There is also a school teacher or a supervisor from the Idaras who observes closely pre-service teachers during practicum. Through teacher practicum, FOEs connect and build relationships with schools and Idaras to serve pre-service teachers’ educational experience through hands-on training. In a study that focused on teacher practicum in four national universities in Egypt (ELKerdany, 2016) results indicated that there is neither link nor alignment between theory offered in the courses at FOEs and school practices through teacher practicum. Salah El Din (2012, as cited in ELKerdany, 2016), stated that what students learn in FOE is either obsolete or inappropriate stating that this

is the reason why MOETE instructional supervisors advise students to put aside what they learnt through their teacher education programme. However, there were few cases that represent examples of good practice at the individual level rather than institutionally. The conclusion of the study referred to the need to evaluate the content offered at FOE in terms of content and pedagogies to be linked to what is expected to teach in schools. Calls for change in pedagogical courses to have them move from traditional teacher-centered to those that are student centred with more links and visits from university professors to schools is needed. Quotations from teachers who were interviewed stressed on the need to look into the gap between schools and FOEs. “There is a gap between what is offered at the FOEs and what pre-service teachers do at schools. Once they enter a school for practicum, they abide by school roles and drop all strategies learnt at the FOEs. This is mainly because supervisors from MOETE review the teachers’ class plans rather than what happens in class” (Safaa, Interview, Feb 20th, 2019).

FOEs and schools seem to be like two different worlds and when they meet there is this perception that faculty members are in their ivory towers with high levels of cultural hierarchy and power given to FOEs over schools. Rarely can you find faculty engaging with teachers and if this happens it takes place at FOEs for one shot training purposes with little engagement from teachers and various levels of resistance as knowledge is always seen to exist with FOEs, not school teachers. The flow of knowledge, the know-how, and experience are top-down from FOEs to schools and seldom vice versa. “We started to understand the school context more and more as this is the first time to be that engaged in school visits with this intensity” (Dalila, Interview, March 4th, 2019). “The link between schools and FOEs is based on the need to collect data and do research” (Sarah, Interview, March 6th, 2019). “Through the project, this changed as I am now aware about school issues and the problems they face” (Mohga, Interview, March 4th, 2019). “Many teachers have potential but are overloaded with teaching hours and routine that limits any opportunity for being creative or innovative” (Latifa, Interview, March 18th, 2019). They do not have any release time for professional development, this is currently not in their mandate. A teacher in the Daffodil school mentioned that he is teaching 8 classes and he is the only science teacher in this school “no way you

can ask him to do other than teach” (Latifa, Interview, March 18th, 2019). Due to the separation between FOEs and schools seeing them from two different worlds, trust was needed to be built at the start of the project “Some teachers were doubtful of our [FOE] intentions when we first started the project, they said that we are here only to take pictures and collect data and say that everything here is okay. It took us time to build trust and that we are one team” (Latifa, Interview, March 18th, 2019).

Section 2

School profile in SUP4PCL project

Fifteen schools were involved in the project in the beginning phases where each FOE partnered with 5 schools within their proximity and according to a pre-set criterion reaching a total of 15 schools. These schools were the core of the professional development schools (PDS) where each PDS later in the project clustered with two new schools to cascade the projects’ concepts and practices, resulting in 15 PD schools per faculty.

Figure 8. FOE and PDSs in SUP4PCL project

FOE profile in SUP4PCL

The project included three Egyptian Universities Ainshams (ANSU), Alexandria (AU) and Helwan

University (HU) from three different locations. Two universities had previous international projects, namely TEMPUS 2010-2013, while ANSU was new.

Table 1

School demographics

School name	Number of teachers	Number of students	Source
<u>AU schools</u>			
Gardenia school	43	520	Baseline report
Iris school	27	407	Baseline report
Heather school	10	409	baseline report
Clover school	45	821	Baseline report
Buttercup school	124	1690	Baseline report
<u>ANSU schools</u>			
Rose school	239	3563	Baseline report
Daisy school	145	1762	Baseline report
Poppy school	68	1237	Baseline report
Jasmine school	116	2320	Baseline report
Dahlia school	30	448	Baseline report
<u>HU schools</u>			
Daffodil school	55	1650	Baseline report
Lilly school	34	815	Baseline report
Lotus school	208	2687	Baseline report
Sunflower school	40	950	Baseline report
Orchid school	32	575	Baseline report

Table 2

FOE demographics

University	Number of faculty-Uni level	Number of students Uni-level	Number of FOE faculty	Number of students	Source
AU	over 8,000	152,305	404	Undergrad 4587	Capacity Development of Faculties of Education in International Approaches to Teacher Education- CDFE/TEMPUS baseline
				Postgrad 4265	(year 2012 -2013)
				Open programs 4830	
			432(staff, demonstrators & assistant lecturers.	11559 (undergrad)	Data obtained from Alexandria University's leadership
ANSU	20000	190000	975	9686	Data obtained from Ain Shams University's leadership
			375	Undergrad 6000	(from kick off meeting PPT)
				Postgrad 1500	
HU	5110 (faculty & assistances)	150000	301	9500	Data obtained from Helwan University's leadership

Section 3

SUP4PCL project intervention activities and the development of PCLs

The project proposed several intervention activities throughout its lifetime. These interventions were organised as per the phases of the project and work-packages set out during the planning and implementation phases. In work-package one, partners in the FOE were required to establish baseline reports including the profile of the faculties of education and school profile. The aim was to identify the current status in terms of demographics, location, mission and vision, organisational chart and cultural aspects that are present in such educational institutions. The project's leadership provided the various teams with the research tools for their baseline studies.

Figure 9. Brief outline of the project milestones

A needs analysis targeted for school teachers was conducted at the beginning of the project. Workshops and meetings between the FOE members and members from the projects' EU partners were conducted to establish momentum and define what is meant by PCLs. They also looked into how to spread the PCL concept and its application in both FOEs and schools through coaching and mentorship sessions. Such sessions helped develop both senior and assistant mentors in the FOEs who in turn developed mentors in the professional development schools (PDS). The school quality assurance units had a main role in this process as units were up and functioning to provide support sessions needed to build on what the FOEs developed.

Work-package two focused on developing material in areas such as science, technology, engineering, arts and mathematics (STEAM), education for sustainable development (ESD) and global citizenship (GC). All three areas were developed with active pedagogies and an emphasis on special educational needs (SEN). This required school visits and workshops to help in both the FOEs and schools on each concept and how to design

material linked to the school curricula yet with a focus on these three new state-of-the-art topics. The project PI and team at AUC developed instruments for such purpose and, in some cases, used previously developed instruments borrowed from ARAS (Action Research for All Schools) which is also managed by MEIHE. FOEs and schools started to document the PCL meetings, workshops and transformation via diaries and reflective practices. Moreover, in work-package two PDS were asked to reach out to neighbouring schools to start a clustering stage (See Figure 8). Work-packages three and four focused on monitoring and policy dialogue. Through these two work-packages, the project activities and interventions were evaluated and outcomes were directly communicated to policymakers at the MOETE and MOHE.

For work-package five on management, the aim was to ensure that the project was well-coordinated and managed at every phase through various mechanisms such as meetings, the creation of a strong website and various other communication conduits. The meetings varied according to the partners involved and aim. There were two types of meetings, local technical meetings, and international management meetings. The former meetings were mainly to support the Egyptian partners at various stages of the project, such as provide FOE members with relevant literature and extended workshops that articulated major concepts in the projects. Examples of these included ethnographical studies, qualitative methodologies, mentorship and coaching, and peer communities of learners. In some cases, the management team at AUC developed exemplary material on STEAM education, education for sustainable development (ESD) and citizenship. These materials were later used by the FOEs in workshops each in their institution to develop similar material for the project at large. Workshops on qualitative methodologies and data analysis were also conducted at FOEs to support their case studies and reporting.

As for the latter type of meetings, international management meetings, these were for general technical issues related to both EU and EG partners in addition to management of the project activities and timeline.

Methodology

The research team decided to use a mixed research method approach with both qualitative and quantitative methods. Cohen and Manion (1994) and Gall, Borg, and Gall (1996) see that using quantitative and qualitative methods increases the validity of information adding richness to the findings, as each complements the other. The qualitative method was, however, more dominant than the quantitative approach in our study. The main purpose of utilizing the mixed methods approach is that it provides a more complex understanding of a phenomenon that cannot be understood by using only one approach alone (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Morse & Niehaus, 2009). The type of mixed methods that this study adopts is a ‘dominant-less dominant status’ type where the researchers conduct a study in a single dominant paradigm with a small component from an alternative design (Miller, 2003; Tashakkori & Teddlie, 1998). Here the dominant paradigm is a qualitative one with a small component from the quantitative paradigm. By utilizing a mixed-methods approach, triangulation is needed to construct an integrated explanation of the phenomenon (Burke, Onwuegbuzie, & Turner, 2007). According to Johnson, Onwuegbuzie, and Turner (2007), the research here falls under qualitative-dominant mixed methods research that Creswell (2012) named as ‘sequential transformative’.

Qualitative research is conducted in a natural setting and therefore enables researchers to learn from the first-hand experience about the world they are investigating (Denzin & Lincoln, 2000). It is also capable of evincing important information that would be relevant for this study as well as providing analysis strongly related to the context in Egypt, which seems to be lacking in quantitative research. The choice of the qualitative methods in this study could be seen in the light of the following description by Denzin and Lincoln (1994, p. 2):

Qualitative research is multimethod in its focus, involving an interpretive, naturalistic approach to its subject matter. This means that qualitative researchers study things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of, or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them.

One of the most appealing methods under the qualitative paradigm is the use of the case study. Creswell (2012) defines case studies as ones that serve the purpose of illuminating a particular issue and provides an opportunity to ‘go deep’ (Corcoran, Walker, & Wals, 2004). The data was collected utilising both quantitative and qualitative instruments between December 2017 and March 2019 to answer the three research questions stated in the introduction and below.

RQ1 What is the nature of the partnership in the project?

RQ2 How does the School-University Partnership SUP impact on practices, beliefs, values, and attitudes?

RQ3 What are some of the tensions between beliefs, values, and practices?

Research Methods

The research throughout the lifetime of the project had various phases where each phase included one or more instruments. The sections below highlight these instruments while stating the aim of each instrument, how it was developed and validated, and details of its structure and how data were analysed.

The figure below shows the timeline of when each instrument was used throughout the four phases of the project data collection (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Project timeline and instruments

Research Instruments

To answer the research questions on the school-university partnership, four research instruments were designed to collect both quantitative and qualitative data. These were: Motivation questionnaire, Habits of mind questionnaire, Focus group discussion protocol, and Individual interview protocol. All four instruments were developed in English then translated into Arabic

when used with the participants. The instruments were back translated to English again to ensure that the wording was not lost in translation.

The following table 3 shows the dates when each instrument was used. It also shows how each instrument is aligned with RQ1 on the nature of the S-U partnership.

Instrument	Date	Alignment with RQ1	Alignment with RQ2	Alignment with RQ3
Motivation questionnaire	December 2017-February 2018	-----	X	-----
Habits of Mind questionnaire	November 2018- March 2019	-----	X	-----
Observations and visits	Ongoing	X	X	X
Document analysis	January-February 2019	X	X	X
Focus group discussions	February – March 2019	X	X	X
Individual interview	February – March 2019	X	X	X

Phase 1: Motivation questionnaire

The first phase of the project involved collecting data through an open-ended questionnaire. The aim of the questionnaire was to identify school teachers' motivation behind joining the teaching profession and capture the level of satisfaction of such a profession. The validity of the questionnaire was obtained by three experts in the field from Egyptian faculties of education. The open-ended questionnaire consisted of two questions, *what is the main reason for joining the teaching profession, and what is the level of your satisfaction with your current profession and why*. The first part of the second question had four options where the teacher would select from. These were 'very much satisfied', 'satisfied', 'somewhat satisfied' and 'not satisfied'. Fifty-five teachers participating in the project responded. Teachers were from the 13 schools where each FOE partnered with the five schools that aligned with the criteria of selection. Seventeen teachers were from AinShams University's three partner schools, 16 from Alexandria University's partner schools, and 20 from Helwan University. Two responses from the 55 were removed from the total as their sheets were left blank reducing the total to 53 respondents. Teachers' responses to question one and second part of question two were analysed using a thematic analysis as described below in all qualitative thematic analyses throughout the project. Thematic analysis approach is a method of analysing, identifying, and reporting patterns (themes) within data (Braun & Clark, 2006). For this to take place, one of the team researchers went through many phases when analysing qualitative data raised from these questions. First, the researcher kept on reading the data noting down initial ideas/codes. Second, data were reduced, and initial codes were generated, this then helped themes to develop. Nine themes emerged for both questions that were analysed qualitatively. Third, the researcher gathered all the data relevant to each potential theme and sorted them thematically. Therefore, the data were organized in thematic categories that represented a rich description. Finally, the researcher focused on analysing the data and providing a concise and coherent finding.

Responses to the first part of question two were done using frequencies as the question was a closed-ended question that was analysed quantitatively. One researcher was responsible for data entry and analysis.

This researcher assigned numeric scores for all 53 participants while keeping the same values of their responses. Before analysing the scores, the researcher considered the proper type to be adopted from this instrument. Consequently, the researcher utilized the summed scores for participants to develop an overall score for each value separately (Creswell, 2012). This overall score helped in providing a percentage to each value that described participants' level of satisfaction and making comparisons. This was done manually. In so doing, a frequency table was created to provide the summative number of participants and the percentage belonging for each value (Bryman, 2012).

Phase 2: Habits of mind questionnaire

In this phase, a quantitative closed four-point Likert scale (strongly disagree = 1, disagree=2, agree= 3, strongly disagree = 4) instrument called 'Habits of mind questionnaire' was administered. The questionnaire was validated and translated into Arabic by researchers in the Action Research for All Schools (ARAS), another funded project led by MEIHE, to accommodate the language needs of the respondents. The questionnaire was validated again in the Erasmus+ project by the quality assurance team. The questionnaire was divided into four main sections, each representing a theme with a total of 72 statements. The themes were as follows: attitudes (14 items), empowerment (18 items), habits of mind (21 items) and philosophy of education (19 items). A detailed breakdown of the four main themes and their sub-themes are in the following table. The number of items was reduced to 34 (25 positive items and 9 negative items) (See Appendix 4).

A total of 68 teachers from AinShams university partner schools were involved, whereas 44 teachers from Alexandria university schools and finally 94 from Helwan university partner schools. Exceptionally, Helwan had included participants from teachers involved in the PCL and non-PCL teachers in their total responses. Tables 3-5 below show the details of participating teachers partnering with each of the three FOEs:

Table 4				
<i>Ain Shams PCLs</i>				
Number of teachers	Number of FOEs	School Name	N	
16	3	Rose School	1	
5	1	Dahlia school	2	
10	3	Poppy school	3	
8	2	Daisy school	4	
12	2	Jasmine School	5	

Table 5				
<i>Alexandria school PCLs</i>				
Number of teachers	Number of FOEs	School Name	N	
5	2	Gardenia school	1	
6	2	Iris school	2	
4	2	Heather school	3	
5	2	Clover school	4	
5	2	Cherry Blossom school	5	

Table 6

Helwan school PCLs

Number of teachers	Number of FOEs	School Name	N
9	4	Daffodil school	1
10	3	Lilly school	2
5	3	Lotus school	3
6	3	Sunflower school	4
5	3	Orchid school	5

Table 7

Habits of mind questionnaire

Code of main theme	Code of Sub-theme	Themes/Sub-themes	Number of items
HM		Habits of Mind	21
	RF	Reflection	7
	AC	Accepting Critique	6
	ADO	Accepting different opinions	4
	CT	Critical thinking	4
	E	Empathy	0
	R	Respect	0
A		Attitudes	14
	G	Gender	2
	D	Democracy	7
	R	Research	1
	CR	Collaborative research	4
E		Empowerment	18
POE		Philosophy of Education	19

Table 8

Habits of Mind responses from Ain Shams University

PCL/non-PCL	School name	No.	Total
PCL in school			N= 33
	Poppy school	13	
	Rose school	9	
	Jasmine school	7	
	Daisy school	4	
Non-PCL in school			N= 14
	Daisy school	14	
PCL in FOE			N= 21
Total 47 teachers + 21 FOE= 68			

Table 9

Habits of Mind responses from Alexandria University

PCL-school/PCL-FOE	School name	No.	Total
PCL in school			N= 11
	Buttercup mentors from the school	5	
	Iris school	6	
Non-PCL in school			N= 25
	Buttercup non-mentors	15	
	Iris school	10	
PCL in FOE			N= 8
		Total 36 teachers + 8 FOE= 44	

Table 10

Habits of Mind responses from Helwan University

PCL/Non-PCL	School name	No.	Total
PCL in school			N= 48
	Daffodil School	8	
	Lilly School	10	
	Orchid school	5	
	Lotus school	19	
	Sunflower school	6	
Non- PCL in school			N= 46
	Daffodil School	14	
	Lilly School	6	
	Orchid school	11	
	Sunflower school	15	
PCL in FOE			N= 48
Total 94 teachers + 4 FOE= 98			

The research investigators of the project aimed to collect responses from the questionnaire from members of both the PCLs and Non-PCLs in the FOEs and schools for comparative purposes. Yet data collected by the team from Helwan university were the only ones who had responses representing such variety and therefore the comparative component of this step was not possible. Responses from each participant were entered by two researchers to an excel sheet with a code that represents the FOE/School; PCL members/non-PCL; code for each partner school associated with its FOE. After this first stage, a cross-checking process took place by a third researcher to ensure the accuracy of data entry. Respondents who left out many questions empty with no responses were marked as 'void' and were disregarded from the analysis. In the questionnaire, statements with negative inclinations were marked using a reverse scoring system as follows (strongly disagree = 4, disagree = 3, agree = 2, strongly agree = 1). Responses were then grouped using descriptive analyses in frequencies and percentages.

Phase 3: Observations and visits

Field notes from school observation visits and FOE visits were collected, reported and reflected on by the project team. The school visits had various aims. One was to observe the classes; the second was to observe the PCLs and their meetings and finally to observe the mentoring processes whether in the partner or cluster school. Therefore, visits ranged from a few hours to full school days on some occasions. During these visits there was a conscious intention to identify the type of leadership found at the school, the functionality of the quality assurance unit, development of the PCL, mentorship process, in addition to any major positive or negative remarks. As for the observations of the FOEs, these were to observe the workshops and to attend and observe the PCL meetings that took place throughout the project. All visits to schools and FOEs took place at different phases of the project where some were more intense than others. In some cases, the visits lasted for a few hours while in others it was a full day of class observation and meetings with PCL groups from the FOEs and schools.

Phase 4: Document analysis.

This phase included analysis of the following documents:

- Monitoring and evaluation reports
- Partner baseline reports
- Management meeting reports
- Reflection diaries
- PCL meeting minutes

Phase 5: Focus group discussion

Focus group discussions (FGD) are typically set to emphasise a specific topic with four to eight interviewees (Bryman, 2012; Creswell, 2012). FGDs provide opportunities to investigate how individuals could collectively make sense of a phenomenon (Bray, Adamson, & Mason, 2014). To ensure clarity and feasibility of the FGD, the protocol was piloted first then adjusted before being administered to the target groups (FOEs and schools). The core research team of four in addition to a student researcher were trained by the PI on how to identify what to look for. The team rehearsed the whole process as a pilot, including what notes to write and how to visualise and map the seating arrangement of the FGD members. The piloting also included an emphasis on observing and documenting the nonverbal communication of participants. Focus group discussions (FGD) were used in this phase to collect data related to both the structure and the process of the school-university (SU) partnership as a focus of research question one, RQ1 'What is the nature of the partnership in the project (in terms of both its structure and process of formulation)' (See Appendix 6). The FGD also aimed to identify various levels of impact of such a partnership between schools and universities.

A total of seven FGDs were conducted with faculty members, school principals and teachers from the partnerships between Faculties of Education and the core partner schools (Professional Development Schools, PDS). The membership size of the FGD, as well as the number of FGDs needed, was determined according to the size of the FOE team. Helwan university had the largest FOE group of 30 members so we chose to have 3 FDGs. Both Alexandria and AinShams universities had between 15-20 members, therefore we had 2 FGDs for each. The following details show when each FGD was conducted and in which school: For Ain Shams university, two FGDs

were conducted as follows: the Rose School (February 20th, 2019) and The Daisy School (February 24th, 2019). FGDs for the partnership between the Faculty of Education at Alexandria University and the partnering schools were as follows: The Iris School (March 5th, 2019) and The Gardenia School (March 6th, 2019). Finally, for Helwan University, three FGDs were conducted as follows: The Lilly School (March 20th, 2019), The Sunflower School (March 17th, 2019), and Orchid School (March 17th, 2019).

Each FGD started with an introduction by the project PI introducing the team members and aim of the FGD. The PI also explained the process of the interview and the consent form needed for video-recording and involvement in the study on a voluntary basis. Questions were all stated in Arabic and the whole discussion was conducted in Arabic. The questions included in the FGD protocol aimed to investigate the nature of the partnership between FOEs and schools and its impact. After each FGD the team had reflection sessions on the main highlights that took place during the FGD and the possible generated themes from the discussions that took place (See Appendix 7).

Phase 6: Individual interview protocol

Interviews were used rather than questionnaires in phase four because of the advantages of the interviews in probing and using in-depth discussions to clarify the interviewee's answers, and probably the interviewer's questions. Robson (1993, p. 228) asserted the following:

The interview is a kind of conversation; a conversation with a purpose. Interviews carried out for research or enquiry purposes are a very commonly used approach, possibly in part because the interview appears to be a quite straightforward and non-problematic way of finding things out.

There are different types of interviews from which the researcher can choose according to his/her research questions and interests. Borg and Gall (1989) distinguished between three forms/types of interviews and the use of each one of them; highly structured; semi-structured and unstructured. This study used the semi-structured interview, which Powney and Watts (1987, p.17) referred to by the term "respondent interview". The interviews were semi-structured that

consisted of open-ended questions. Fontana and Frey (2000) describe semi-structured interviews as "one of the most powerful ways in which we try to understand our fellow human beings" (p. 645). The semi-structured format allowed for a discussion to take place with the interviewer and the order of the questions differed according to the flow of conversation. This structure also permitted to explore the perceptions of the respondents and to follow-up on any new ideas (Seidman, 2006). The interview questions focused on the impact of the partnership in the participants' education settings and how it transformed their professional learning practices. The reasons for selecting semi-structured interviews were three-fold. Firstly, to ensure that the thematic areas identified in the study would be covered with all the interviewees. Secondly, to have the flexibility to move from one question to the other, adding if necessary other questions, according to the interviewees' responses. Thirdly, to provide better chances for the interviewee to elaborate on his/her answers rather than a yes or no answer. In this way, the interviews might be seen as a conversation and less intimidating to the interviewees helping them talk freely.

To ensure clarity and feasibility of the individual interview questions, the protocol was piloted first then adjusted before being ready to be administered to the target groups (FOEs and schools). One question was removed from the final version as it seemed to overlap with an existing one. The individual interviews were conducted in Arabic and started with a number of questions related to biographic information. This included questions related to gender, age, area/s of specialty, duration of involvement in the project, years of experience and finally the educational institution which the interviewee is affiliated to. A total number of 19 questions were asked which focused on the impact of the partnership project through questions that related to the following themes: reflective practices, empowerment, teaching strategies, sense of belonging, and teacher to student relationship (See Appendix 3 for details). Interviews were conducted at the same location where the FGD took place yet in separate private rooms where each interviewee was comfortable to respond to the questions. The interviews were conducted by either the PI or Co-PI in the presence of a research assistant who helped take notes and audio-record the interview. Based on the focus group conducted in each

S-U partnership, participants who were less likely and hesitant to speak and share ideas comfortably were the ones interviewed (Riemer, 2011). The interviews were also conducted with those whose time permitted them to stay after the FGD. The sampling was intended to be purposeful at the outset of the study, yet this was not always possible. In some cases, sampling was based on convenient selection due to time and availability limitations.

Approval of audio-recording was obtained. Each interview lasted from 40-60 minutes. A total of 14 interviews were conducted with faculty members from FOE while a total number of 17 interviews were conducted with teachers in the partnering PD schools. From the 31 interviews, 23 were females while 8 were males. In some instances, further probing questions were required to ensure that all questions were covered. After the interviews were conducted and recorded, responses were transcribed in Arabic (same language used during the interviews). To ensure validity of the transcription, a sample of the transcriptions was sent back to the interviewees to ensure face validity. The researchers selected one faculty member from each

FOE to review, edit and comment on their responses documented in the transcript. None of the interviewees had changes to make. Their only comment was related to punctuation rather than content of the responses. All transcribed interviews were approved by their respondents. The details about the interviewed faculty members and teachers are in table 11.

The interview questions included a focus on the nature of the partnership as worded in RQ1 through the following 3 questions mainly related to the process of the partnership.

1. Which Events/seminars did you participate in during the lifetime of the project?
2. What professional support did you receive in your learning during the lifetime of the project?
3. How do you describe your mentorship style? (Please give examples)

The interviews also aimed to identify various levels of impact of such a partnership between schools and universities.

Table 11

Demographics of Teachers (n=16) and Faculty (n=15) members participating in the interviews

	Gender		Age range				Average teaching years	Specialties
	Male	Female	20-30	31-40	41-50	Above 50		
FOE	2	13	3	6	6	-	13.5	1 Curricula and instruction faculty in each of the following: Math, French, Science, Arabic, Philosophy, Technology, Biology, Special education, English, 1 Applied linguistics 1 Teaching English as a Foreign language
School	6	10	1	4	7	4	20.75	4 Arabic, 3 English, 2 Math, 2 Social Studies, 1 Teacher in the following: History, Media, Chemistry and Geography

Triangulation

Triangulation is the most common way in qualitative research to seek validity. Validity indicates that an instrument studies what it claims to study and that the results and theories produced are true. The validity of this research was supported in different ways. Firstly, all instruments were piloted in advance of use (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2000; Teijlingen & Hundley, 2001). Secondly, all interviews and focus group transcripts were checked by some participants prior to inclusion in the data analysis process. Thirdly, as many people as possible were included in each phase of the research to ensure a variety of perspectives were represented. In reference to triangulation, Silverman, (2000, p.177) refers to triangulation as "...[an] attempt to get a 'true' fix on a situation by combining different ways of looking at it or different findings". Robson, (1993, p. 290) had earlier noted that there are other purposes of triangulation, such as the "complementary purposes model.... [where the researcher uses] different methods for alternative tasks". This study used triangulation by multiple methods to cross-reference the collected data. Denzin (1978) described four types of triangulation techniques: data triangulation, investigator triangulation, theory triangulation and methodological triangulation. This case study is utilizing the following types of triangulation namely methodological, investigator triangulation and data source triangulation. The first type of triangulation was methodological triangulation as both quantitative and qualitative methods to investigate one specific phenomenon. Different methods were used including one-on-one interviews, focus groups, and field note observations to increase the trustworthiness of inferences (Guba & Lincoln, 1985). The second type was investigator triangulation. Both Denzin (1978) and Patton (1990) referred to triangulation by investigator as data can be collected from different people as data providers. In this project, data were collected from teachers and principals in schools in addition to faculty members from the three faculties of education involved in the project. Data were also collected by different people from the project team and at different timings throughout the lifetime of the project. There was more than one researcher who collaboratively collected and analysed the data, in which reflections, discussions, and comparisons were collaboratively made to determine the consistency of results across multiple subjects. In addition to the designed instruments and data collected

from each, the research team conducted school observations and document triangulation. The latter was done in mid-January 2019, when two researchers extracted responses from management meeting reports, faculty members' reflective journals that aligned with the focus of questions from the draft versions of the interview and focus group questions. They both manually colour coded the source of responses, for example, any data/parts from transcripts were under the colour green, etc... Meetings were held with the PI to reflect and discuss the findings. The PI mentored the researchers on where to put certain parts and directed them on some questions that were difficult to be placed. This process helped better understand questions in the FGD and interviews thoroughly. Both researchers worked individually then met to discuss, reflect and ask each other questions to check for mutual understandings. Throughout the research process and during the analysis, both types of triangulation were used to increase validity. Such variety of data through triangulation enhances credibility and conformability.

Participants

In qualitative research, the sampling strategy is usually chosen based on the methodology and topic, and not by the generalizability of the findings (Higginbottom, 2004). The sample of this study included teachers in the participating schools and faculty members at the faculties of education under the partnership agreement. Three faculties of education and 13 schools formed the sample group of this study. The three faculties of education were AinShams University, Alexandria University, and Helwan University. As for the 13 schools, they were all given pseudonyms to ensure anonymity. Members from the faculties of education and schools were selected using a convenient sampling method involving participants based on their availability (Creswell, 2012; Gay, Mills, & Airasian, 2009). All schools referred to in this study were given pseudonyms. All participating teachers and faculty members were also given pseudonyms to ensure anonymity.

A second level of sampling was conducted to administer the focus group interviews. The FGD was done according to the size of the FOE team to determine how many FGDs were needed. Helwan had the largest FOE team of 30 so we chose to have three FGDs, while

Alex and Ain were 15-20; therefore, we had two FGDs.

A third level of sampling was conducted to select participants in the individual interviews. Interviewees were selected using a purposeful sampling method at first. It then changed to a convenient sampling due to teachers' time limitation and availability.

In general, the sampling in this study followed a 'multilevel sample design' where the study involves two or more sets of samples obtained from different levels of the study (Collins Onwuegbuzie, & Jiao, 2007).

Access to the Research Sites

Access to the research sites was obtained through a series of steps that started with signing a memorandum of understanding (MOU) between two ministries, the ministry of education and ministry of higher education. Each faculty of education involved in the project also had to seek approval of the local educational directorate to allow their access to schools. Since Egypt is well known for its centralised educational system, access to the research sites could only have happened through this heavy security system (i.e. top-down). Principle investigators with their core teams at each FOE helped secure entrance to schools throughout the lifetime of the project.

Ethics and Approvals

In the initial stages of the project, discussions on data collection and research led to unfolding some cultural issues in terms of the sensitivity of requesting signed consent forms. One way of overcoming this was to request oral consent to participate in the research. Discussions amongst team members of the project as a whole, involving members from European countries in addition to those from Egyptian universities, led to agreeing on following the British Educational Research Association (BERA) ethical guidelines in addition to the need to follow institutional research guidelines (Institutional Research Board [IRB]) and others related to conducting research in Egypt (Central Agency for Population Mobilization and Statistics [CAPMAS]). Instruments utilised throughout the project were administered at a point in time where trust was built. For example, both FGDs and interviews were conducted after nearly two years since the start of the project which allowed for participants to open up

in their responses. All participants in this study signed a consent form as part of the IRB requirements. They were told at the beginning of the data collection that their consent is needed and assured them that data will only be used for research purposes, hence the names and data from participants will be kept anonymous and confidential (see Appendix 6 for IRB consent form). The researchers walked the participants through the form to ensure clarity and that participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw at any point during the study. Only those who approved to be part of the study were included. It is important to note that none of the teachers in either schools or faculty members refused to take part in the study. In addition to the IRB approval, CAPMAS approval was needed as part of the research requirements in Egypt (See Appendix 5).

All raw data were kept confidential as aligned with IRB requirements where only the PI, Co-PI and 2 researchers had access to it. The files and transcripts were saved on computers that were password protected to secure responses.

To ensure transparency and validity of the data collected through focus group discussions and interviews, a sample of the participants was sent back their transcripts for approval. Part of the responsibility of the researchers in this study is to keep the participants informed of the outcomes. Meetings and debriefing with FOE members and peer-reviewing of the draft findings are means used in this study. The final results are published and shared with FOEs and schools. This is also part of the dissemination plans in the project.

Data Analysis

Data collected in this study included both quantitative and qualitative data. A hybrid of both inductive and deductive analysis were carried out. The former was through pre-set frameworks while the latter took place through bottom-up generated themes as a result of the data analysis. Quantitative data collected by the Habits of Mind instrument was entered into excel sheets and analysed using descriptive analysis (frequencies, means and standard deviations). Two researchers carried out this task to ensure accuracy of the data input. As for the qualitative data, the nature of the data requires a more dynamic, intuitive and creative process of inductive reasoning (Basit, 2003). Such reasoning

helps “interpret and structure the meanings that can be derived from data” (Thorne, 2000, p. 68). Therefore, when conducting data analysis, the researcher becomes the instrument for analysis as to making judgments about coding, decontextualizing and re-contextualizing the data (Starks & Trinidad, 2007). Braun and Clarke (2006) distinguish between two levels of themes: semantic and latent. Semantic themes ‘...within the explicit or surface meanings of the data and the analyst is not looking for anything beyond what a participant has said or what has been written” (p.84). In contrast, the latent level looks beyond what has been said and ‘...starts to identify or examine the underlying ideas, assumptions, and conceptualisations – and ideologies - that are theorised as shaping or informing the semantic content of the data’ (p.84). Braun and Clarke (2006) also distinguish between a top-down or theoretical thematic analysis, that is driven by the specific research question(s) and/or the analyst’s focus, and a bottom-up or inductive one that is more driven by the data itself. For them, six steps are needed to go about the data analysis as follows: Become familiar with the data; Generate initial codes; Search for themes, Review themes; Define themes; and Write-up.

The first step was employed by two researchers who read the qualitative responses in both the FGDs and individual interviews. Each researcher transcribed and analysed responses which led them to generating initial codes from going through the data as the first step in making sense of the large amounts of raw data (Creswell, 2012; Dey, 1993). A second round of reading the full transcripts was done by the PI and Co-PI who after meetings and discussions led to reaffirming the initial codes and generating new ones as well. All disagreements were discussed until a consensus was reached. Moreover, during the write up phase more sub-themes emerged which were discussed in draft form with the team. The analyses, in general, took several iterations till the final themes were generated and agreed by the research team that consisted of four core members and a student researcher as they reached saturation (Fusch & Ness, 2015).

Figure 11. Data Analysis Spiral
Source: Creswell, (2009)

In addition to following the thematic analysis as stated above, Toulmin’s model complemented the process. Toulmin’s model or so-called ‘system’ utilises an *inductive argument model*. Inductive arguments have reasons that lead to probable but not certain conclusions. Such arguments move from the bottom up and from the particular to the more general. Toulmin’s model consists of six constructs as in the figure below.

Toulmin’s argument pattern (Toulmin, 1958)

Figure 12. Toulmin’s model
Source: Erduran (2007)

According to Toulmin a claim is a statement which contains structure and is presented as the outcome of the argument. Data is an utterance, which constitutes the evidence. It may refer to either past events, information about the conflict situation at hand, or the communication exchanged between the two parties. As for the warrant, it is an utterance that is used as a rule, principle, premise or inference-license and acts as a bridge between the data and the claim. The warrant indicates the relevance of the data to the claim.

Backings are generalizations making explicit the body of experience relied on to establish the trustworthiness of the ways of arguing applied in any particular case. Rebuttals are the extraordinary or exceptional circumstances that might undermine the force of the supporting arguments...qualifiers are phrases that show what kind of degree of reliance is to be placed on the conclusions, given the arguments available to support them (Erduran, 2007; Simosi, 2003). This model is closer to the latent level of thematic analyses.

Limitations

The research is not without limitations; some relate to the type of research design namely case study. The main limitation of case studies relates to the limitation of generalising the findings due to its contextual

nature (Sim, 1998). Nonetheless, the intent of this study is not to generalise results but to understand the context and how this is reflected in the data findings. Cronbach (1975) argued that no research outcome is generalizable after accounting for local, contextual conditions. There were contextual limitations related to accessibility to the research locations due to schools and faculties of education being occupied at various timings of the year for exams and grading at the end of the semester and end of the year. It was also not possible to carry out observations throughout *all* phases of the study due to time limitations, access and approvals to visit sites, school days were short, and exams in schools.

The Process, Structure, Outcomes and Impact

Process

The inception phase

The very first step in the process of fostering a school-university partnership began with the FOE teams visiting the schools that were selected by the local MOETE directorates in partnership with the three faculties once the security clearances had been obtained. The steps undertaken by the faculties were to first introduce the project to the schools and the concepts of professional development, enacting partnerships and of creating Peer Communities of Learners (PCLs). The next step was to conduct a needs assessment study with a school profile to familiarize themselves with the schools. In a third instance, faculty members conducted weekly or regular visits to the schools, which were largely mentorship sessions and Continuous Professional Development (CPD) for the introduction of new pedagogical practices and teaching concepts.

The process of the initial visits began in the summer of 2017 after the FOEs had prepared tools, with the support of AUC, to conduct rapid ethnographies of each school as well as a needs assessment tool. The first encounters were mostly fraught with a great deal of scepticism and resistance as reported by Egyptian faculty from the three universities. School teachers reacted by saying we have been trained so many times before and these trainings were useless.

The schools represented a wide range of urban educational contexts and cultures. Obviously, the diversity gave rise to differentiated reactions to the partnership. Like in many parts of the world, those schools that had the most difficult circumstances in terms of socio-economic conditions of the students, classroom density, teacher shortage and disciplinary challenges were the ones least desiring the partnership and resisting it till later stages of the project. This was observed by the AUC research team while conducting a focused group discussion in the Lilly School after two years of the life of the project. Both the observations by the team and the accounts during the focused group discussion led to the belief that the Lilly school was particularly challenged with regard to teacher shortage,

class density, and student discipline. There seemed to be a culture of violence and misbehaviour in that school. The teachers who met with us described the faculty of education mentors as being highly idealistic and romantic when suggesting teaching strategies and solutions to classroom management. One quote which clearly represented the views of all the teachers was when one teacher stated that “we have discussions with the mentors and they suggest things to us that do not work for this school as their suggestions do not match our reality” (Focus Group Discussion in Lilly school on March 20th, 2019 with teachers and faculty members from Helwan university).

Moreover, those schools with the greatest amount of involvement and support from their leadership were the keenest on the partnership. During a focus group discussion with the Peer Community of Learners PCL group in the Sunflower school in a suburban area, several teachers commented on the benefits of the partnership and one of them clearly stated that “the exchange of experience between our school and faculty members from the university has clearly led to us discovering new talent in our school that we had not noticed in the past.” The Sunflower school is one which enjoyed outstandingly supportive leadership as asserted by the staff in the school who described their leader as a woman with vision and a sense of commitment to a cause and who always stood behind them and supported their innovations. (Focus Group Discussion on March 17th with school teachers and faculty from Helwan university). Similarly, in the Jasmin school in another suburb, members of the PCL were very aware of the benefits of the partnership and clearly expressed those in several meetings and in the recently produced school magazine (Visit and Focus Group Discussion on March 11th with members of the school PCL and a mentor from Ain Shams University).

Schools with a long-standing research relationship with the university also manifested signs of keenness to continue the partnership. Moreover, those schools in general that create a partnership around participatory action research to solve some of the school problems in many cases manage to flatten power relations and hence strengthen and improve the partnership (Wood & McAteer, 2017). Members of the Rose school had for some time been engaged with a faculty of Education in a participatory action research project

which involved school teachers and faculty members. During interviews and a focused group discussion, members of the school PCL clearly expressed their excitement about the partnership. Galwat, a senior school teacher, admitted that when the faculty team arrives at the school she and her colleagues literally jump and run down the stairs in utter excitement to meet them as every moment brings with it some learning. Every detail of the encounter is so rich so they record it on WhatsApp and share it with the whole school (Interview with Mrs. Galwat a senior teacher at Rose school, February 20th, 2019). Moreover, still in the Rose School who had expressed how much they valued the learning with and from the university faculty, during a recorded discussion members of the Peer Community of Learners PCL explained how three of the teachers had been transferred to other schools and yet despite challenges, remoteness and their busy schedules, they continued to attend the regular PCL meetings at their old school (Focus Group Discussion, February 20th, 2019).

All in all, the faculty of education manifested greater interest in the partnership at first than the public schools. Looking at several case studies of school-university partnerships this does not seem unusual. The level of desire often seems unequal between both institutions normally favouring the university faculty (Osajima, 1989). Trust was not sufficiently built at that early stage. Many teachers were suspicious of what the faculty could offer given that they were classified as being theoretical, irrelevant and mostly living in their ivory tower. Teachers in the Lilly school clearly expressed their thoughts about the situation when stating that faculty in university may be strong in reading, gaining knowledge and research however when it comes to dealing with primary school students deeply plagued with violent behaviour those professors do not know what to do and they do not have the answers or experience (Focus Group Discussion from the Lilly School on March 20th, 2019). Many of the teachers could not relate to a partnership that they perceived as taxing on their energy, time and other resources when their salaries were so low and level of appreciation negligible. During several visits to the Daisy school with mentors from university between December 2018 and January 2019, during discussions school teachers bitterly complained about their very low salary, the lack of appreciation from authorities

and their general low status. They made it very clear that to fulfil the terms of the partnership they needed to be exempted from some of the tasks they were required to do at school. The mentor from university in charge of the Daisy school reported that teachers resisted the meetings and the formation of a PCL as they felt at first it was not useful and also it taxed on their time. They said they could make better use of their time. This was of course especially true in a context where many teachers were engaged in private tutoring.

In addition, those teachers that felt powerless were most likely not to welcome the partnership. Ishak from the Daffodil school explained that he suffered from many problems such as low salaries, no incentives, in addition to a feeling of powerlessness and not being appreciated. In his own words, he explained that “as a teacher I am completely frustrated I feel like the system is neglecting us so we abuse each other, then teachers abuse parents and finally they abuse the students” (Interview, March 18th, 2019). The power relations between school and university were perceived as asymmetrical such that there was no acknowledgment of the various ways of knowing. People who feel their knowledge is being respected are more likely to believe in their capacity to change their reality (Wood & McAteer, 2017).

Evolution phase: Building rapport

Those faculty and teachers who had a sense of empowerment and regarded themselves as agents of change were more open to the partnership and saw opportunities for reform. Members of the Rose team were very proud of being part of the SUP4PCL project and had in fact designed their own logo for the project. Salwa a seasoned teacher from the Rose school declared “most teachers are interested in making more money, this is not me. I would like to be able to change things and renew myself” (Interview, February 20th, 2019). Dr. Jameela a mentor from University described the team from Rose school as having been totally convinced that together they could bring about transformation (Interview with Dr. Jameela, February 20th, 2019). The teams from the Rose school and those from the Gardenia school attested to the fact that they had transformed and changed into a culture of trusting and sharing ideas (Focus Group Discussion in Rose school, February 20th, 2019, and Focus Group Discussion in the Gardenia school, March 6th, 2019).

Ola from the Iris school another example, clearly stated that the project contributed to increasing her sense of empowerment and urge to transform her school (Interview March 5th, 2019). This relationship between empowerment and the willingness to join a partnership for the sake of reform and transformation seems to be true of other contexts (Osajima, 1989).

Several important approaches and events warmed up the partnership. Some continued to support the partnership grow and yield fruitful results whilst others caused a setback but were quickly rectified and reversed the negative impact. The first approach was building rapport. The faculty mentors visiting the schools had been very well-coached throughout the various activities (work packages) in the project and hence were for the most part very humble and mindful of the classical divide and hierarchy between the two institutions and strands of knowledge; theory and practice, and thus, they focused on building very personalized relationships at first before moving into the professional domain. This process of building rapport took time. They socialized and shared food and drinks together. This clearly broke the ice and yielded positive results in some instances faster than others. In addition, the faculty mentors explained to the school teachers that they were genuinely interested in their needs and ideas on how to enhance them professionally. In an interview, Nawal, a teacher from the Daisy school, complained that teachers had been neglected for very long and their capacities underestimated. The fact that the partnership project paid attention to them and acknowledged their potential, meant the world to them (Interview with Nawal, February 23rd, 2019). Meanwhile Mosaad a male teacher from the Daffodil school stated that “it was the first time ever that university came to school to listen to us and hear our opinions. This brought about rapid results and signalled to us that the university people care about us” (Interview, March 18th, 2019). Ishak a middle-aged teacher also from the Daffodil school expressed his support of the project as he stated “now we have a voice that will be heard” (Interview with Ishak, March 18th, 2019). The university mentors truly applied all the signs of humility that Freire would advise for mentors and leaders entering into dialogue whereby people regardless of their level and status are getting together to genuinely co-construct knowledge and attempt together to learn more than they know (Freire, 1970). Academics would learn more about

practice and practitioners more about theory. Finally, the university mentors were able to manifest genuine empathy for the complexity and challenging jobs teachers had. During a focused Group discussion in the Rose school (February 20th, 2019), teachers attested to the great respect they received from the very junior faculty members who mentored them. The senior teachers noted how these young mentors showed a great deal of humility. In the Iris school, (Focus Group Discussion, March 5th, 2019) the faculty mentors in the PCL admitted to their past ignorance of the complexity and heavy load teachers carried while performing their calling. They now saw the reality of a teacher’s life within their own environment in schools. They offered their empathy and felt that they wanted to share in carrying this tremendous load. Teachers in the same school expressed their deep gratitude to the feelings expressed by the mentors and declared that this was sufficiently motivating and satisfying even when the mentors were not always able to present them with solutions to their many challenges and problems. Dr. Latifa a mentor from University expressed her empathy with the teachers’ hardship, expressing her emotions she stated “I am so excited to be in the field and to witness the difficulties teachers encounter in schools” (Interview, March 18th, 2019). These same feelings were expressed on numerous occasions during our field research.

The nature of the activities planned out by the project allowed for some direct contact with international faculty during workshops and seminars at the university. This was very much appreciated by both Egyptian faculty and school teachers. During the focus group discussion held with the Sunflower school PCL (March 16th, 2019), teachers testified to the great benefit they had experienced from meeting the European experts and partners in the project. They actually pointed out that they had specifically noticed the team spirit among the European team and wished to emulate it. They remembered the names of the international mentors and wished to see them more often. The Rose school expressed the same sentiments and more (February 20th, 2019).

Establishing teacher labs at university

The project had initially promised the schools some equipment such as laptops and data show. Unfortunately, this was later not allowed by EU regulations hence all

the equipment was placed in the faculties of education. This at first shook the trust and disrupted the smoothness of the relationships, however it was very quickly turned into a positive development when the university teams established labs on their premises which they devoted to the school teachers. The teachers then felt respected and enjoyed the fact that they were now more frequently connected to the university especially when they were invited to workshops and seminars that took their expressed needs into account and made them feel that they were listened to. Nawal from the Daisy school declared that she had been very well supported by her mentors and that whatever idea she shared with them their response would be “let us make it happen” (Interview, February 24th, 2019). More importantly the relationship became even stronger when many teachers and faculty had a great sense of empowerment as manifested by the innovations they were able to bring about in the schools. Mohga a university mentor for the Iris school announced her sense of great empowerment by virtue of being charged with transforming a school with her other colleagues in the team “each one of us brings in our own ideas” (Interview, March 4th, 2019).

Consolidating and institutionalizing the relationship: teachers in the driver’s seat

In the Rose school during a focus group discussion, one teacher declared that she was new in the school and noted that in comparison to other schools she had worked in, the training and quality assurance unit was very effective and was able to spread all the new ideas from the university mentors to the whole school (February 20th, 2019). The teachers from the Daisy school had come up with an innovative idea namely to invite the students in school to go visit the university

and write an article for their media class where they would interview faculty and visit the university library and faculty of education. The university mentor took on the idea and started to prepare for the activity (Focus Group Discussion, February 24th, 2019). In many situations, the teachers were beginning to be in the drivers’ seat when determining the topics to be discussed in their meetings. During a focused group discussion conducted with the teachers and faculty mentors of the Rose school, teachers were asserting how there were no topics presented or discussed during their regular meetings that had not emerged from the teacher’s expressed needs. They recounted the instances and topics that had been in response to their requests such as learning and teaching strategies and aids. They would always, in fact, hang all the training aids and presentations on the walls of the training unit space so all teachers could benefit, and to them it was also a way of advertising the existence of the school-university partnership they were so proud of (Focus Group Discussion with the Rose school teachers and mentors, February 20th, 2019). The faculty mentor in the Daisy school explained how each of the mentorship sessions and PCL meetings had a different topic that he insisted be selected and determined by the teachers in the school (Interview, February 2nd, 2019). Finally, the relationship in the process of collaborative development became stronger as the administrative staff and middle-range policymakers became more involved in the partnership. This is true of Deans of faculties of Education as well as Directors of Ministry of Education local departments and administrations as well as supervisors.

Looking at the literature on Professional Development Schools it would seem that some of the phases of developing collaboration between university and schools were short-circuited in the process by the project objectives and activities. In other words, the partnership had developed institutionally through a project that was largely initiated by MEIHE in partnership with the faculties of education. Hence, the first two phases of *formation* and *conceptualization* were already predetermined by the project which aimed at creating 45 Professional Development Schools, 75 school mentors, 75 targeted peer communities of learners, enhanced and developed quality assurance units in the 45 PDSs, as well as classroom materials focused on STEAM, Global Citizenship Education, Sustainable Development and Special Education, Needs SEN. The other three stages towards collaboration namely; *development*, *implementation* and *evaluation/reformation* were done in concert with all stakeholders who had an interest in the collaborative relationship (Dixon & Ishler, 1992). Through several local and international technical meetings, the partnership reached consensus around the thematic areas of intervention and the modality of work which focused largely on multisector teamwork based on student-centered pedagogies of active learning and relying on inquiry and research. Moreover, all team members agreed on the value of collaboration and building partnerships. They also agreed on the significance of egalitarian and empowering relationships. Although the process was not totally homogeneous in all instances with some schools reaching a very high level of trust and collaboration with the university, it may be quite safe to observe that the partnership had evolved quite steadily through several stages on the continuum of trust, collegiality, professional development and community with learning and a commitment to growth and inquiry at its centre. We tend to agree with others that becoming a school-university partnership with a PDS model is not an either-or matter nor is it without setbacks, but rather it is a prolonged journey of becoming measured on a continuum of trust and collaboration and all the essential features of a successful partnership (Parker, Parsons, Groth, & Brown, 2016).

Structure

“There is no single “right way” to establish a partnership” (Callahan & Martin, 2007, p.143).

Goodlad (1998) defines partnerships as “a deliberately designed, collaborative arrangement, between different institutions working together to advance self-interest and solve common problems” (as cited in Handscomb, Gu & Varley, 2014, p.12). In the case of enhanced partnerships, these are usually seen as complex, adhering to fuzzy processes where the views of the various stakeholders and their respective contributions are seen as carrying equal weight and value (as cited in Handscomb, Gu & Varley, 2014).

As mentioned in the introduction, partnerships in the PDS model evolve through many levels. Regardless of the level attained, the nature and structure of each school-university partnership may be classified in accordance to an endless number of characteristics and variables (Callahan & Martin, 2007; Day, 1998; Handsomb, Gu, & Varley, 2014; Reed, Kochan, & Ross, 2001). We will select the most relevant of these in order to be able to design a profile of the nature of the Egypt SUP4PCL partnership.

In accordance to the **leading institution in the initiative, hierarchy, power and the direction of decision making and the change patterns. Unilateral versus reciprocal change patterns.** In other words, whether the partnership is university-driven, school-led or co-developed in neutrality. Normally the power relations here play a role as there is the perception of a hierarchy of knowledge wherein university is always in the dominant position while school-based knowledge is regarded as inferior. This description of the definition also takes into account the decision making patterns. In the case of the SUP4PCL project it was made clear from the onslaught of the partnership that not a single institution or partner would wield power over the other. All voices would be equally heard. Through the interviews and FGD we noted the gradual breaking down of the hierarchical barriers. Hence while at the beginning, admittedly the initiative and decisions were made by the university, as the partnership became more developed and solidified, power relations were levelled and more decisions as to the subjects of professional development and dialogue were being mutually decided upon and in fact on many

occasions led by the school teachers. Dalila a faculty member from Alexandria mentoring teachers from the Gardenia school expressed herself during an interview on March 4th, 2019 “the partnership is a very special and positive experience it has taught us to break down hierarchies and to deal with each other as human beings regardless of academic levels and degrees even among the teams at university,” Several teachers on the other hand during all focused group discussions mentioned that whereas at first the agendas and meetings were set by faculty members, teachers very soon had a voice and expressed their needs while selecting the topics to be handled during workshops and meetings.

In accordance to whether it is based on individual **relationships and collaboration** or **institutional** ones in a **structured** way. In other words, whether the communication and dialogue was a structured one occurring between institutions and not individuals. In some PDS models the collaboration emerges as a result of one or more university faculty members building relationships with school practitioners for the purpose of research or the advancement of practicum. In the case of the SUP4PCL initiative, the partnership was truly institutional and developed its own structure. The partnership was designed in accordance to a signed protocol between the National Ministry of Higher Education and the Ministry of Education. Moreover, the relationship between each university and the schools appended to it was regulated by signed letters of agreement and protocols between the university and educational district bureau. Each University created a team of 12-24 faculty and a clear structure for mentorship where each school was endowed with from 1-4 mentors, depending on size. Meanwhile each school in collaboration with the university mentors created a Peer Community of Learners ranging from 5-20 teachers and practitioners in each school. Various tools were employed to establish databases and also to identify professional development needs of teachers and school practitioners. Other tools were developed for the purpose of initiating and sustaining reflection amongst teachers and educators whether individually or collectively. A few of the university mentors made reflection a regular practice amongst their school PCLs after each meeting or mentorship session. Meetings and mentorship sessions were held regularly almost once a week and workshops were formally organized both in schools and at university with the involvement of the

training and quality assurance units in the schools. The training and quality assurance units were instrumental in spreading and replicating the workshops held on a wider scale in the school.

In accordance to **the focus of the partnership** and the declared goals and objectives. In other words, whether it is Initial teacher education, Continuing professional development CPD, or consultancy and collaborative research. In the case of SUP4PCL, the purposes discussed and declared in several of the meetings have been, maximizing student learning through the development and implementation of exemplary practice, engaging in sustained reflection and inquiry on practice for the purpose of enhancing *exemplary practice* and student achievement and engaging in meaningful ongoing professional development CPD, to prepare effective new teachers. The project was clear about the various roles; thus faculty at Egyptian faculties of education were to be coached by European faculty in an egalitarian environment of exchange. Meanwhile Egyptian faculty from university were to mentor school teachers. Teachers were also expected to mentor their peers, especially when expanding the school clustering networks. Of the four ordinances and principles of PDS namely the preparation of new and veteran teachers, university faculty development, inquiry directed at the improvement of practice and last but not least, enhanced student achievement, the most pronounced in our case was the first one in the form of Continuous Professional Development CPD for teachers and practitioners, along with university faculty development. Both these two were essential targets. The third mission statement or principle of inquiry directed at the improvement of practice this is slowly emerging in the project as teachers are preparing to participate in the end of project conference. Since February 2019 all university mentors initiated workshops and mentorship sessions to introduce inquiry and research to the PCLs in their schools. Prior to that date in December 2018, five of the partner schools to Alexandria university were invited to participate in a workshop on action research organized by the Middle East Institute for Higher Education MEIHE from the Graduate School of Education at the American University in Cairo. The schools were initiated into research and those participating in the workshop were encouraged to spread the training to others in their schools as well as the 13 schools they were to cluster

with in the current phase. Since the summer of 2019 in June, all mentors were engaged with school teachers to conduct participatory action research. As for the fourth mission namely enhanced student achievement this was clearly the objective of all PCLs as expressed in the seven focus group discussions conducted as well as the interviews. Indicators on the achievement of that objective are further discussed when looking at impact.

In accordance to **the type of outcomes**, in other words, whether it is ideological transformation, capacity building, or generativity. The SUP4PCL initiative had a little bit of all these typologies developed by Christopher Day (Day, 1998, p. 815). Mentors from the university were keen to develop some form of ideological homogeneity amongst the teachers particularly with regard to activity-based learning, cooperative learning and integrating curriculum and lesson plans. In addition, the project had introduced such themes as Global Citizenship Education, sustainable development and the STEAM approach. It had also drawn attention to the importance of special needs education and the celebration of difference. The following figure 13 clearly portrays the ideological inclination of the project and was used as a guideline for the development of materials. It encompassed subjects, environment and dimensions of learning.

Figure 13. Project conceptual framework

In addition to the ideological transformation, the element of capacity building was quite pronounced whereby the leaders of these projects were trained to

become change agents and through a process of challenging but supportive dialogue over time, led by a credible, authoritative and empathetic team of university mentors, there was a rise in professional and personal self-confidence. These and many other results will be discussed in more detail in the section devoted to outcomes. The generative aspect of creating joint research had materialized in one of the schools through another project supporting action research, however there are continuous efforts to expand the outputs of the partnership to that level of generating research.

The level of complexity. The SUP4PCL initiative proved to be quite a complex undertaking. Some remind us that if classroom teaching is complex, which we all admit it is, how much more complex is the work necessary for building partnerships within a PDS model, one that takes into account different institutions with their diverse cultures, different contexts, different stakeholders and even different teaching traditions (Dresden, Blankenship, Capuozzo, Nealy, & Tavernier, 2016). The project invited on board several and diverse stakeholders rendering the partnership truly complex. Although the initial partnership involved only faculties of education in the selected universities, schools in the Helwan, Alexandria and Ain Shams district proceeded to contact other faculties for an expanding partnership especially faculties of science and medicine to promote their newly acquired skills in integrated teaching and learning. Hence, other faculties became stakeholders. Moreover, at the university level, the core teams reached out also to other disciplines beyond their own departments such as language, English literature and beyond. Students in all schools became visible stakeholders of the partnership and very soon they were themselves visiting the university premises and joining the school PCL. Student teachers from university also eagerly joined the partnership and on several school visits were visibly engaged and joined the mentorship/training sessions offered at school. The training and quality assurance units of each school were very much part of the partnership and in almost all the schools the focal person of the unit was also a member of the school PCL.

On the international level the partners in the initiative from the United Kingdom, Ireland, and Germany were very much present in all the various significant dialogues with school teams on mentorship, material

development, and the formation of PCLs. The international partners were also partnered with the Egyptian faculties of education in a twinning arrangement. At first, the partnership between the European and Egyptian universities was generic and amorphous. With time a purposefully designed and AUC led twinning arrangement was established between Helwan and Martin Luther universities, Alexandria and Northampton, Ain Shams and Limerick and finally the American University and Leicester. The twinning involved all kinds of activities with a mentorship component and allowed the partners to move to significant domains of inquiry, research and professional development. These twinning arrangements were sealed with formal Memorandums of Understanding for sustainable partnerships. Policymakers were also part of the mix as ministry heads of departments for quality assurance, training and supervision were all included in the complex mix. Several information sessions and activities were created to strengthen the partnership with middle-range policymakers and school supervisors were always invited to workshops. On the national level the policy dialogue also continues through various channels such as committee meetings in the Supreme Council of Universities SCU, meetings with policymakers and high-level officials at the Ministry of Higher Education MOHE, as well as policy meetings with high-level officials at the Ministry of Education and Technical Education MOETE. Key issues placed on the policy table are largely how to create sustainable partnerships, how to mainstream the school-university partnership movement and how to create policies and structures to support the reform approach. Media is often invited to schools and is a growing partner. Last but not least, parents and communities were invited into the partnership particularly with regard to special needs education sensitization as well as inviting parents and the community to support their children when engaged in integrated and multidisciplinary learning. Not only have the relationships expanded to all the above-mentioned stakeholders, but in addition a system of school clustering was established whereby each of the original mother schools was clustering with three other schools in the same district with the aim of expanding the partnership and the learning across many more boundaries. Hence, complexity comes with multiple complex relations, stakeholders, contexts, and what proponents of complexity theory have called an ‘As-

semblage’ to signify the connection between all these components. Some have suggested that for the success of partnerships and PDS, complexity might be deemed necessary: “To produce innovation, more complexity is essential; more relationships, more sources of information more angles on the problem” (Rosabeth Moss Kanter, p. 148; Delueze & Guattari, 1987; as cited in Dresden, Blankenship, Capuozzo, Nealy, & Tavernier, 2016, pp.70-71).

In accordance to the **mode of learning**; whether it is **periodic or continuous**. The SUP4PCL model is one that has developed virtuous circles of ongoing learning. The meetings and mentorship sessions have been very regular. In fact, in all situations, university mentors have visited and had mentorship sessions at least every other week. In Helwan, while teachers meet every week at school, mentors visit every other week. In the other universities, both in Alexandria and Ain Shams, the mentorship visits and sessions take place every week. These regular sessions are not withstanding the more formal workshops taking place in schools or universities. In Helwan, the total amount of such workshops reached 69. Most of the topics are demand-driven and emerge out of an avid appetite for learning amongst practitioners. One senior teacher is quoted to have expressed her deep gratitude during an interview when she stated “I am so grateful to God that I was able to learn new things before I retire” (Interview with Galwat a senior teacher in the Rose school on February 20th, 2019). Salwa from the Rose school during a focus group discussion declared in public “I have never missed a single session or meeting since the project began, we are learning so much” (Focus group, February 20th, 2019). This statement of how much teachers were learning in all domains was repeated in all interviews and focus group discussions. Faculty members also attested to how much they were learning about the practical side of teaching and the professional lives of teachers.

The topics around which the workshops were organized were many, rich, diverse and covering a lot of ground. Examples of the various topics mentioned during the interviews and focus group discussions were: Leadership, integrated teaching, and learning, active learning, technology for enhancing learning, peer learning, cooperative learning, diversified learning strategies, the STEAM approach, Global citizenship Education, Education for Sustainable development, Special Needs Education, effective

communication, building and understanding character and personality. In all the universities, a school technology lab was established and placed in multi-purpose rooms where many activities take place with the support of the equipment procured by the project and the facilitation of university faculty. These labs have been instrumental in strengthening the process of school clustering and have also been very significant for the development of integrated teaching materials with the help of technology.

In accordance to the **geographic location** of the partnership and whether it is co-located with the university. The literature on PD schools makes a very clear distinction between this model of partnership and laboratory schools that were first initiated by John Dewey early in the past century. In the case of the former, the partnership occurs with already existing public schools that are administered by an educational directorate or a district. The latter is usually built within the vicinity of a university hence collocated and is run by the faculty of education. The latter model focused on creating civic democratic students whilst the former was more concerned with developing effective teachers and exemplary teaching (Arnold, 2015). As earlier mentioned, our model for the SUP4PCL initiative follows the Professional Development School model and hence unlike the laboratory schools the partnership schools are not situated on the university campus but are within the neighbourhood of the selected three universities with the partner faculties of education in most cases.

The conditions for selecting the partner schools with the faculties of education included geographical proximity, willingness to participate, the existence of quality assurance and training unit with preference given to those schools that already had some sort of ongoing relationship with the university through action research or other forms of inquiry. It was also important that the schools, even when belonging to the same educational administration, would represent some degree of diversity both in terms of level of performance as well as the socio-economic conditions of the students and communities. This indeed created differences in the varying levels of maturity of the partnership which was also mitigated by the nature of the leadership in each situation and within each of the partnering institutions.

In accordance with the **nature of the relationship** whether it is one relying on information diffusion, supportive facilitation, or close cooperation (Day, 1988). What started as a long negotiation and brokering of a relationship between faculties of education and schools progressed in its stages of development to move from the university mentors diffusing information to a stage of supportive mentorship and facilitation finally reaching a strong structure in most cases of close cooperation with clear engines and drivers of change. The influential engines used in our model were the introduction of university mentors and the coaching of school mentors, both of whom invested in the creation of Peer Communities of Learners (PCLs) who in turn acted as self-contained interactive and home-grown mentors amongst themselves. Finally, the university mentors introduced inquiry and action research as a third engine in the more advanced stages of the partnership. Ultimately, these engines and processes created what some have called *synergistic relationships* within the partnership. These relationships focused on *immediate assistance* in the form of mentorship sessions and workshops on demand such as engaging the teachers and members of the PCL in activities and classroom instruction involving educational technology. The relationship also focused on exchanging curricular ideas wherein the faculty members and teachers engaged in the creation of curricular materials around Global Citizenship, STEAM, Sustainable Development and Special Education Needs SEN. Both faculty and teachers engaged in establishing integrated curriculum and subject matter whereby teachers from different disciplines were able to work together and create lesson plans and teach in classrooms in teams and in an integrated fashion. Finally, those kinds of relationships resulted in what some have called *professional nudging*, development, scaffolding or mentorship whereby faculty members as well as teachers were able to observe and consult each other as they prepared and delivered their classes. They were even in many cases able to share resources and borrow references from the faculties of education (Gilles, Wilson, & Elias, 2009). It must be however clarified that partnerships varied in terms of how much they reached this level of collaboration and reciprocal interaction.

In accordance to whether it is an **exclusive or expanding partnership**. The evidence from the research shows that it is expanding in regards to the school teachers

who are not part of the school PCL and yet are invited to join. During the focused group discussions many of the school teachers came to ask if they could join the partnership and learn more about it. Moreover, a specific question during the discussion addressed that very point and asked the participants to comment on whether their partnership PCL was a closed or open one and in every single instance the answer was clear that it was a very inclusive and expanding partnership that not only invited more teachers but also the school leaders and administrators, the students and their parents as well as members of the community. In several of the schools, the partnership had expanded to reach out to other faculties at University such as the school of medicine, science and administration. A teacher leader in the Sunflower school in the Helwan district, declared that since their students were now developing projects around science and environmental issues they felt a need to reach out to the school of science, medicine and management. In Alexandria, the principal of the Iris school, who had led a school-wide team on a sustainable development project to do with water conservation, declared that he was in conversation with the department of science and engineering for a partnership. At the university level, the respondents all assured us that other faculty members and departments were encouraged to join the partnership. In fact, some members of the PCL and school mentors were not from the faculty of education; they belonged to other department such as English literature. Even more assertive of the expansive nature of the partnership was the school clustering that began in January 2019. Each of the original five schools in the SUP reached out to two more schools in the neighbourhood or in the same educational district. The schools were selected largely through the choices made by the leadership in each of the schools taking into account their networks of relationships and of course the clustering was blessed by the Ministry of Education as an accepted strategy for reform. Many of the teams from the original schools and mentors from the Faculties of Education

FOEs, reported that the second layer of partnerships was smoother and that the cluster schools responded quite readily to the offer as the idea of SUP was by then spreading. The team from the Sunflower school during the focus group discussion (March 16th, 2019) mentioned that although they had prepared a whole lecture on the resistance to change as an entry point for the first encounter with the cluster schools, anticipating that they might meet resistance, the first encounter in fact went very well and the partnership was created. The same comment was made by the Ain Shams team during a workshop initiating the relationship with the cluster schools on April 11th, 2019 and the Alexandria team employed their teacher's lab at the faculty to trigger weekly Saturday meetings to bring on board the cluster schools to the partnership.

In summary, one may define the partnership emanating from the SUP4PCL project as one that is egalitarian in nature, structured, focused on Continuous Professional Development (CPD) at the school and university level, engaged in continuous and cooperative learning and aims at transformation. The partnership is in addition quite complex while continuing to expand. One can safely generalize these attributes of the partnership to 13 of the original 15 schools that went into the first stage of partnership in the project. Two of the fifteen schools namely the Poppy and Dahlia schools have not gone through the process and continuum of formulating a partnership due to weak mentorship and other issues confronting the team at Ain Shams University. As a result, the definitions reached do not apply to those two at the time of writing this case study, while they apply to all thirteen in varying degrees. As agreed earlier, reaching a Professional Development School partnership is not an either-or matter but rather is a situation of becoming on an extended journey and continuum of success. We believe the two schools mentioned will join the other 13, sooner rather than later.

Outcomes and Impact

Outcomes represent an area that has admittedly been neglected in the literature on partnerships and professional development schools (Special Issue, School-University Partnership, 2016). The case studies from the SUP4PCL project are looking at outcomes from various angles. All case studies with the exception of the current case study, are focused on the emergence and strengthening of Peer Communities of Learners (PCLs) and their impact on the teaching and learning in both school and university institutions. (See appendix with the research questions and teams responsible for each). This case study is attempting to have a close look at the totality of impacts as a result of the partnership. It assumes that one of the key results is the creation of Peer Communities of learners as will be demonstrated by all other case studies. Peer Communities of learners that straddle school and university institutions were, in fact, one of the driving engines of the partnership. All the interviews and focus group discussions conducted for this case study indicated that Peer Communities of Learners had indeed been formed in varying degrees in 13 of the schools and all three Egyptian faculties of education in addition to the American University in Cairo.

In looking at outcomes, we would like to employ the concept of *marginal improvements* that rely on the fact that individuals, schools and educational institutions change slowly and oftentimes only partially. Moreover, the changes are often uneven given the large diversity of reform stakeholders. More importantly, it is crucial we recognize that change comes in small steps that need to be recognized and made visible as we track the road to successful transformation (Reed, Kochan, & Ross, 2001).

Examples of marginal improvements on the road to transformation as a result of school and university partnerships were:

Blurring of boundaries between higher education and k-12 personnel

This usually means that there is evidence that teachers are taking a greater role in the development of the PDS, are engaging more in research, professors are learning some classroom pedagogies from teachers in their university teaching (For boundary-crossing see article by Sewell, Cody, Weir & Hansen, 2018 on the

diagram on seven affordances p. 329). In the case of our SUP4PCL project, both teacher educators and school teachers collaborated to produce integrated lesson plans and classroom materials around STEAM, sustainable development, global citizenship and Special Education Needs (SEN). The production of those materials occurred during joint workshops where university faculty from Egypt and Europe joined school teachers in the development of those materials between December 2017 and December 2018 to be continued in summer of 2019. This process clearly took into account the seven affordances mentioned by Sewell, et al., (2018) namely; building relational trust, making shared values visible, willingness to share power and expertise, responding to school context, promoting dialogue, setting manageable goals and resourcing them.

Instances, where the boundaries were being clearly blurred between both types of institutions, is when faculty of education mentors admitted to learning a great deal more about the context of school they were responsible for. This not only allowed them to respond to the school needs but also enhanced the research they were able to do with the collaboration of teachers. On the other hand, several of the school teachers mentioned how they had managed to co-supervise practicum students from the university and invite them to their teams for solving problems at school and create improvement plans. This was especially true when it came to special needs students (Focus Group Discussion in the Daisy school February 23rd, 2019). Most teachers expressed their joy at being able to go to university again and acquire new ideas, while some FOE mentors claimed they were now learning new teaching strategies from the teachers in schools (Focus Group Discussion from the Lilly school, March 20th, 2019).

On building relational trust during the entire journey of building the partnership, the university mentor from the Daisy school declared that when he confronted any problems in his profession or otherwise in life he would turn to his newly found teacher colleagues in school (Interview, February 24th, 2019). Several of the teachers and mentors mentioned that their relationship together had become very tight to the extent that they socialized, went shopping together and when any of them was ill or hospitalized members of their PCL came visiting. Dr. Latifa from the university who was

responsible for mentoring teachers in the Daffodil school mentioned that when her son was hospitalized all the school teachers came visiting and were very supportive (Interview, March 18th, 2019). This same mentor mentioned that they now called each other by first names and had clearly flattened all signs of hierarchy.

Still on doing away with hierarchical relationships, a PhD candidate teaching in the Iris school, explains “the two institutions need each other, teachers need university to continue learning and the reverse is true” (Interview, March 5th, 2019). Galwat a teacher in the Rose school declares “we are very pleased to observe how much closer theory and practice have become. We have been promised to be invited to lecture at the university” (Interview, February 20th, 2019). This was confirmed by Dr. Dalal from the university in question, who during an interview declared that she planned to invite the teachers from the Rose school to present in her classes and talk about their professional experience (Interview, February 23rd, 2019).

The field research results were replete with instances where it was clear that dialogue and communication had become a way of life among the teams and had become greatly enhanced. It had also become a modality between professors and students at university. Meanwhile, technology was now being used as a conduit to dialogue and share all their practices and news. Preferred channels were WhatsApp, Edmodo and WebQuest.

Renewed sense of professional identity

Teachers now spoke of each other's work in the partnership with a great sense of pride. They are happy to showcase the work of colleagues. A teacher from the Rose school during a focus group discussion very proudly gave credit to her colleague, a chemistry teacher, and acknowledged her for leading the preparation of integrated lessons on water that also touched on sustainable development (Focus Group Discussions February 20th, 2019 & March 16th, 2019). Some teachers admitted they had been previously involved in private tutoring but have now stopped and have developed closer and responsible relations with their students. In fact, some teachers invite the weaker children during school vacation to support them and give extra tutoring for free (focus group discussion in

the Sunflower school 16.3.2019). Marina a teacher in the Iris school in Alexandria declares “now that I work with others I have developed a sense of belonging and feel a great deal more confident. I now feel a greater need for making autonomous decisions in my teaching” (Interview, March 5th, 2019). The same feelings were echoed by Ola from the same school, Nabila from the Rose school, Dr. Jamila a mentor from university, Dr. Safaa from the same university, Alaa an MA student from another university, Dr. Donia, as well as Dr. Elham from the same university.

Gaining a sense of renewal at both the university and school level

In addition to the powerful quote earlier mentioned of the teacher who was so grateful to renew herself and learn something new about her profession before retirement, Ishak a young teacher from the Daffodil school maintains, “this project is truly wonderful it is allowing me to grow and develop. I am now reading a lot more and preparing my classes with greater care while having the opportunity to consult with colleagues and university mentors” (Interview, March 18th, 2019). Salwa a teacher from the Rose school declared, “I feel like a student again and it is wonderful” (Interview, February 20th, 2019). A teacher from the Sunflower school informs us that she is enrolled in a diploma on STEM in university and uses everything she learns there in her classroom teaching at school (Focus Group Discussion March 16th, 2019).

School administrators involving others in decision making

Despite the usually very hierarchical and centralized system in schools with authoritarian styles of leadership, some of this was gradually giving way, in some situations, to different forms of management. Teachers in the Sunflower school claimed that the climate at school had now become wonderful, “our school principal gives us positive energy. She encourages us to take decisions and be creative and always says I am backing you all.” The school principal herself had joined the PCL and declared that all the good work we were observing was a result of the great teamwork in her school (March 16th, 2019). We did observe on some other occasions similar management styles in schools, however we cannot claim this to be the norm in the 13 schools being reported on. In fact, in some situations the

school management style was a challenge confronting the maximal functioning of the partnership.

Training unit involved and its capacity is built

From the inception, the design of the SUP4PCL project made sure that the training units established by the Ministry of Education in each school become involved in the enactment of the partnership and its aims. In almost all the schools, the training unit director is a member of the peer community of learners that straddles the school-university partnership. Many teachers during the interviews and focus group discussions mentioned that although the quality assurance and training units were rather weak and inactive in most schools, in the professional development schools of the partnership they were very effective and as some had mentioned “a new life has been injected in those units” (Focus Group Discussion with teachers and mentors of the Rose school, February 20th, March 20th, 2019). The director of the Sunflower training unit discloses how she transmits all the learning obtained through the partnership to the whole school (Focus Group Discussion, March 16th, 2019). As for the daisy school, the teachers explained that the training unit took the lead in clustering with the next three schools. It was the training unit that trained and approached the members of the new schools entering the partnership.

Engaging parents and community

At the Daisy school the English teacher who was assigned the whole area of Special Education Needs SEN, recounted how she had been mentored by the faculty to engage parents and community. She explained how she had organized workshops to bring the parents on board and sensitize them on how to deal with children having special needs. She had even gone beyond the parents and held those meetings with the community at large. She had created some partnerships with the community and held events with special needs children and their families (Focus Group Discussion with teachers and mentors from the Daisy school, February 23rd, 2019). In the Lilly school, the university mentors had guided the teachers on methods of creating partnerships and awareness campaigns with the community to decrease violence (Focus Group Discussion, March 20th, 2019). Teachers at the Rose school recount how they had formed agreements and partnerships with parents to jointly

create learning aids for the children (Focus Group Discussion, February 20th, 2019). The same was true of the Orchid school where parents not only offered their help on learning aids but also volunteered to be in the classrooms (Focus Group Discussion, March 17th, 2019). Galwat from the Rose school involved her own family in creating teaching and learning aids for the children (Interview, February 20th, 2019). Clearly at the various different schools the concept of inclusion was becoming an expanded one. It not only minded the narrow mandate of disabled children but had a much broader perspective of inclusion which signified redistributing quality education to all children, giving voice to communities and other stakeholders and taking account of differences while using the support of the resident teachers (practicum teachers) from university (Waitoller & Artiles, 2016).

Engaging students in the partnership and allowing students to teach their peers

Most teachers and faculty members attested to the fact that they engaged their students in the partnership activities. Many faculty members had created PCLs with their own students. In schools, some teachers involved students in the development of improvement plans (Focus Group Discussion with teachers and mentors from the Sunflower school, March 16th, 2019). Teachers from the Orchid school recounted how they had learned a great deal from faculty mentors on sustainable development and had become very passionate about the topic so they engaged their students in related activities to the topic (Focus Group Discussion, March 17th, 2019).

Deep levels of transformation

The above areas portray some of the impacts from the partnership and the project. Change and transformation can be classified at different levels of depth. Some have classified those into three levels (Parker, Templin, & Setiawan, 2012):

- Changes involving surface level, such as revised learning and curricular materials as well as technologies.
- Changes involving new teaching approaches as manifested in active learning, classroom management, lesson planning, and different strategies employed. As a general observa-

tion from those researchers who have gathered data on PD schools, there is a general consensus that teaching tends to be more constructivist, child-centered and cooperative than traditional schools (Ross, Brownell, Sindelar & Vandiver, 1999).

- Changes at a deeper level reflecting the transformation in values, attitudes and beliefs as well as habits of mind, manifested in practices such as **sharing of information, mentorship, collaboration, co-teaching and team teaching** and most importantly **reflection**. Reflection takes different shapes and types such as interactive reflections with others, individual contemplative reflection, action related reflection, research oriented reflection, social reflection and subject knowledge reflection (Day, 1998). Some of those can be done in writing and others orally. This level of deep change will also be looking at the sense of **empowerment** as well as teachers' philosophies of teaching and learning. Also very significant at this level of change and transformation is moving from **extrinsic motivation** for improved teaching and learning to **intrinsic modes of motivation** for providing an exemplary education. As Fullan emphasizes, motivation is at the heart of the change process (Arnold, 2015).

Finally, a significantly deep level transformation is with regard to **professional identity and confidence**. Professional identity has been defined as the "extent to which someone thinks of his or her professional role as being important, attractive and in harmony with other roles". Teachers' enhanced and positive image of self often overrides the challenging conditions in which they work (Beijaard, Meijer & Verloop, 2004, p.119). This also relates back to crossing boundaries when teachers become involved in research and inquiry.

Levels of change and transformation in the SUP4PCL project

At the surface level, all teachers in the schools had undergone changes as they had introduced new themes in their school curricula, such as sustainable development, global citizenship education, and STEAM. Moreover, they had all received mentorship on the use of new

technologies in the classroom and had in fact enacted and used those new learnings starting from the use of PowerPoint all the way to moviemakers, flipbook and other more sophisticated technologies. They had also learned to connect and maintain their PCL activities through technologies such as the use of Edmodo and WebQuest.

On a more profound level of change and transformation clearly, both faculty and teachers had acquired new pedagogies. During a focus group discussion teachers explained how they had moved away from traditional teaching and had become a lot more student-centered, "we now invite students to work with us. During our training we learned how to stimulate different children with different personalities. We have now developed better strategies for dealing with children" (Focus Group Discussion with teachers and mentors from the Sunflower school, March 17th, 2019). Dr. Elham, on the other hand, from university, admits that she is very new to teaching and started her teaching experience with the project. She proudly announced how much she learned and has been using concepts acquired from the project in her teaching at university such as creating group work among her students as well as applying STEAM and multi-disciplinary approaches in her lectures. She admits having observed from the European experience and teams that what matters is values and skills more so than subject matter and as a result she now listens a lot more to her students. She tailors her classes to respond to their life experiences (Interview, February 2nd, 2019). Dr. Mamdouh, a mentor from a different university, explains how his teaching as a result of the project changed. He now applies cooperative and active learning in his classes (Interview, February 24th, 2019). Dr. Rania from the same university admits, having heard about Peer Communities of Learners for the first time through the project (Interview, March 18th, 2019). Dr. Somaya from a third university confirms the same experience and has started now to form a PCL with her students. She also uses active learning strategies in her classes. Also from the same university Dr. Dalila noted that in her classes, due to the use of new teaching strategies and the use of new technologies, students have become more engaged and their evaluation of the classes improved (Interview, March 6th, 2019).

Changes at a deeper level were manifested by the team adopting **new habits of mind**, new **values and beliefs**. Also significant was the development of **collaboration** and **reflection** all of which allowed

for *innovations*. The teams were now very eager to share information among themselves and not only that, but they now referenced and gave credit to the initiators of ideas. In the Sunflower school, a teacher refused to take credit during a public event for the high performance of the students at school and very eagerly gave credit to her colleague who had been responsible for the students' high performance (Focus Group Discussion with teachers and mentors from the Sunflower school, March 16th, 2019). Another teacher in Alexandria explained how she referenced always an innovative classroom strategy she borrowed from a colleague for incentivizing students. Teachers are now also very eager to impart values they acquired to their students such as honesty, sharing their work, patience and being supportive and caring of others (Focus Group Discussion with the teachers and mentors from Iris school, March 5th, 2019). Many teachers from the various schools also mentioned they had learned to accept others, deal with them and even trust them.

On another level faculty and teachers had deeply internalized collaborative behaviour. Dr. Dalila from a university declared that she now believes that collaboration is so much better than competition (Interview, March 6th, 2019). Also, from the same university, Dr. Mohga has grown to appreciate collaborative work to a great extent and plans to go into collaborative research and team teaching (Interview, March 4th, 2019). Dr. Aleya from a second university teaches a technology class with other colleagues from different specializations (Interview, February 24th, 2019). Likewise, Dr. Safaa from the same university recounts how she invites colleagues to sit at the back of her classes to observe her teaching and give her feedback (February 20th, 2019). Alaa, an M.A. student from university, collaborated with a professor from Martin Luther University in writing a paper for a conference in Italy and is, as we write, presenting the paper (Interview, March 3rd, 2019).

Many of the school teachers expressed their appreciation of collaboration and explained how they had learned it from their university mentors who manifested great collaboration and teamwork in their mentorship. Teachers in the Sunflower, Lilly, Daisy, Rose, Orchid, Gardenia, Iris and Daffodil schools practiced integrated and team teaching. A variety of topics lent themselves to such integrated and

collaborative planning and teaching. Topics such as water within a sustainability framework were taught by chemistry, language, religion, geography and history teachers. Tourism and ancient monuments in Alexandria were being collaboratively taught by language, math, geography, art and history teachers. A lesson about palm trees was also being taught by a number of subject matter teachers and many more such examples. Galwat from the Rose school asserted that "the best part of this project has been teaching us to collaborate together as teachers. We are now passing this on to the students and employ group and collaborative learning in class" (Interview, February 20th, 2019).

If anything stands out as a very deep impact of the project, it would be the ability and willingness of faculty and teachers to practice reflection. Many of the teachers reflect during lesson planning, during teaching, and after teaching is over. Quite a few write their reflections regularly. Some even use reflective diaries (Interview with Atta from university, February 18th, 2019). Ola, from the Iris school, uses her diary to score her daily achievements every day as a method of self-motivation (March 5th, 2019). Some use reflection as a prelude to metacognition that they later transmit and use with students (Interview with Nabila from Rose school, February 20th, 2019). Ebtissam, from Iris school, informed us that they now teach their students to reflect (Interview, March 5th, 2019). Similarly, Dr. Latifa, from university, requires her students to practice reflection (Interview, March 18th, 2019). The same is true of Dr. Jamila from another university (Interview, February 20th, 2019). Both Dr. Jamila and her colleague Dr. Dalal believe that reflection has enhanced their research ability (Interview, February 23rd, 2019). Many had never done proper lesson planning before, but now they invested time and effort reflecting and preparing very detailed and intricate lesson plans. Dr. Rania, from university, has not only learned to reflect through the project, but now plans for her lectures in writing and in advance (Interview, March 18th, 2019). Dr. Mamdouh, from another university, says, "reflection is very much part of my daily practice now. I do it in writing and also use technology. When I video tape I add my own reflections on" (Interview, February 24th, 2019). Dr. Safaa from the same university says it has become an integral part of her personality (Interview, February 20th, 2019). Whereas, Dr. Donia from another

university ranks reflection as the greatest impact from the project (Interview, March 20th, 2019). Several of the faculty members in universities engage in group collective reflection. Looking at the quantitative results of the interviews conducted, with regard to the closed questions asking participants to rank which area seemed to have the highest impact on them, 57% of all faculty members believed that the area most impacted was the self in learning and teaching. School teachers also scored highest on the self in learning and teaching and reached 53% of all responses. This particular component entailed issues such as the underlying values for their teaching and learning philosophy such as belief in rights, equity, democracy, and participation. It also included the underlying assumptions and perceptions of learners. It most importantly very much touched upon their reflective practices and how it impacted their teaching and learning.

Clearly reflection, collaboration and the general climate created by the project resulted in *innovations* in classrooms and schools at large. Many new ideas were being implemented such as the complaint box, the school journal, and a coupon system to incentivize students who were well disciplined. Many teachers encouraged their students to recycle materials and use their creativity to produce new objects.

Some teachers use gaming in teaching while some schools have initiated block scheduling. For assessment, some teachers have introduced student portfolios. At the university level, technology has many uses and some faculty members use it to monitor their practicum students through blogs. Faculty members have introduced research courses with particular emphases on action research in their undergraduate level for the first time along with innovative pedagogies.

The closed questions in the interviews showed that the partnership has impacted the participants in their teaching practices to a very large extent. For teachers, it was the next item after reflection scoring 35%, and for faculty, it ranked as a third but important item at 21%. Both teachers and faculty attested to the fact that the innovative practices and initiatives, as well as the changes in teaching and learning, were due to a very robust system of mentorship put in place.

Mentorship in the project appeared in many forms; there was formal one on one mentorship, group mentorship,

peer mentorship and even online mentorship. Teachers in the Lilly school expressed their very deep gratitude to the university mentors. With their support, they have learnt and practiced the integration of subject matter as well as new themes such as Global Citizenship. They also had practiced and learned new teaching strategies that had led to greater student engagement even in classrooms that had sixty students or more. In that same school, teachers also recognized the impact of peer mentorship on lesson planning (Focus Group Discussion, March 20th, 2019). Teachers from the Sunflower school expressed their gratitude to the university mentors and how that resulted in developing their own mentors in school. One of their school mentors won an award for being the best mentor in the whole district. In the same school, teachers also admitted to the great benefits acquired from being mentored occasionally by the European partners (Focus Group Discussion, March 16th, 2019). A teacher from the Rose school declared: “it is so wonderful to live this experience of cooperation and partnership. We have been far from the university for so long and we need to keep in touch...we also learned so much from our exposure to the Europeans”. Teachers explained how they also benefitted from the practicum students on field training in their school, who not only taught them new strategies but also facilitated borrowing books from the university library which helped them create their own materials (Focus Group Discussion, February 20th, 2019).

International literature and reviews indicate that mentorship is indeed a great way of improving teachers’ self-efficacy and professionalism. The good coaching and mentorship not only lead to higher levels of empowerment, but also have great positive impacts on the organizational culture of schools and other comparable institutions. An additional impact of good coaching and mentoring is the visibly increased reflectivity at the institutional level (Lord, Atkinson & Mitchell, 2008). Coaching and mentoring have positive effects on the mentors and are regarded as professional development for them (Hudson, 2013). More importantly, mentorship not only leads to teacher empowerment, mentor and teacher learning, and transformation, but also proved to have an impact on the quality of student learning and ultimately student achievement (Ali, Wahi, & Yamat, 2018; Smith & Lunch, 2014).

In the next few paragraphs of this section, we will be examining three more deep levels of transformations and outcomes namely; the sense of *empowerment*, and largely related to that and previous sections on the evolution of educators' professional identity, is the way in which their motivation for learning and performing proved to be largely *intrinsic* which can become a significant factor in the sustainability of our initiative for reform. Lastly also very much related to those two deep levels of outcomes is the way all this actually impacted the *students and their achievement*.

Quantifiable results from the tool, measuring empowerment, new habits of mind such as reflection, and philosophy of education, show that the respondents from the various universities and professional partner schools were well aware of concepts such as reflection and mostly practiced it before, during and after performing an activity. Respondents had acquired those attitudes towards teaching, assessment, and relating to students that had a proven record and evidence of success in the literature on good practices. They chose the responses that indicated a good understanding of progressive pedagogies such as allowing students to learn at their own pace, having good relations with students, measuring their progress over time not necessarily through testing, and encouraging lifelong learning. Finally, the results also show they had a sense of empowerment and felt that they could work at professional development in their institutions, they could meet with parents when needed, they were collaborative, helped colleagues and could practice participatory research in their institutions.

The qualitative results from the interviews corroborated those results particularly with regard to *empowerment*. Both teachers and faculty members revealed that they had been greatly empowered professionally and personally by joining the partnership. Ebtissam, from the Iris school, expressed how very empowered she felt by the new positive culture that is encouraging collaboration, which is emerging in her school. She reported feeling a lot more confident and had developed a great sense of self-efficacy. She felt she could make things happen. She also admitted feeling like an agent of change and had acquired power through the love expressed in the team and the positive energy (Interview, March 5th, 2019). Ola from the same school had the very same feelings (March 5th,

2019). Galwat from the Rose school believed that she had truly become empowered by virtue of obtaining student engagement (Interview, February 20th, 2019). Dr. Latifa from university declared that she believed the whole management style of the project was indeed very empowering (Interview, March 18th, 2019). Dr. Jamila from another university, who felt so empowered by the partnership, declared

“I am still very junior at university and no one usually listens to me, but when I go to my school, the ideas I present are so well received and with the school team, we are able to implement them. It is very rewarding and empowering. I would like to be an agent of change and I do feel that with time I can contribute to the changing of values in the school culture” (Interview, February 20th, 2019).

Dr. Dalal from the same university and team confirms that “I feel most empowered at school because we are a very united team- we are one hand and we support each other. When I look at my reflection diary, I realize how much I achieved” (Interview, February 23rd, 2019). Similar quotes can be pulled out from the other two universities. Dr. Donia, from one of the universities, believes she has become an agent of change with her own students (Interview, March 20th, 2019), likewise another member of the mentor team in a second university explains how empowered she felt through her relationship with Martin Luther faculty when she was able to publish an article in German in a peer-reviewed journal (March 16th, 2019). In the third university, the coordinator of the project, who is also a school mentor, felt greatly empowered to lead her team even though many of them were quite senior to her. She feels that she now has a voice at the university level and is a strong agent of change (March 6th, 2019). Much of the literature on teacher and educator empowerment emphasize that this is usually a state of being that occurs as a result of greater decision making possibilities, professional growth, improved status among colleagues, self-efficacy and having an impact (Sparapani, Mackay, Fuchs, Voydanoff, Pietras, & Rogers, 2015). Moreover, the research also points to the fact that with increased participation in learning communities a sense of empowerment results (Dail, Goodsite, & Sanders, 2018).

The renewed professional identity, successful mentorship, change in the organizational culture and sense of empowerment led to many teachers and mentors seeking satisfaction through achieving success with students and collaborating with peers. One could depict how motivation was now increasingly growing through altruistic and intrinsic values of why they were committed to their profession. The teachers in the SUP4PCL project had been asked to respond to a questionnaire in the middle stages of the project between December 2017 and February 2018, in which they were asked to explain why they joined the profession. Against all expectations and traditional perceptions of why teachers go into the profession, out of the 53 respondents who participated in the study the vast majority had joined the profession not out of pragmatic reasons or extrinsic motivation, but out of a sense of pride and belonging to the profession and the values and beliefs they upheld. It, therefore, did not come as a great surprise to discover that with the existing values teachers expressed, their *intrinsic motivations* would increase in tandem with the professional and career development they were receiving (Liu, Li, & Zou, 2018). The results of the questionnaire also showed that teachers were satisfied and content with their current occupation. They were continuing to be motivated in the partnership despite all the very many challenges. They were joining activities simply because the activity was satisfying and or enjoyable (Gultekin, & Acar, 2014).

Lamis, a teacher from the Lilly school, claims to be much more motivated to practice reflection and do research on her own teaching, as she noted it made a difference in student performance and engagement (Interview, March 20th, 2019). During focus group discussions with teachers in the Rose school, it was clear that they all willingly participated in mentorship sessions and were very keen even though there were no financial or any other tangible promotion incentives (February 20th, 2019). Safaa a teacher in the Rose school describes how motivated she is by the project. She is very attached to the project team. She, in fact, wishes to sustain all the transformational gains made including the formation of the PCL and all the collaborative work that ensued (Interview, February 20th, 2019). Ishaq from the Daffodil school explains “It is not about more money; I really genuinely want to learn”. Ishaq has in fact signed up for further graduate

studies at the university as a result of the partnership (Interview, March 18th, 2019). Still within the same school another colleague, Mazen says, “the real prize and trophy I take away from this experience in my school is that my students are learning, have achieved good results and have become well behaved”. Mazen expressed how much he enjoys his work with students and the love they express to him. It pleases him to observe how much they enjoy his classes. Although his school is one of the very disadvantaged ones with a lot of students practicing child labour and living in a pervasive culture of violence (Interview, March 18th, 2019). Dr. Latifa who is the mentor in the Daffodil school admits to the hard circumstances of the school and says “when I met these teachers with such difficult circumstances and such high potential I became very motivated to contribute and support them. I identify very much with the aims of this project”. She then went on to say, “My team and I have invested a great deal of effort for this partnership so we would like to see it continue and become sustainable” (Interview, March 18th, 2019). Dr. Mohga, a mentor for the Iris school, mentioned during an interview “we are learning so much from this project at all levels which is what motivates us to continue to work so hard” (Interview, March 4th, 2019). Dr. Dalila, a mentor for the Gardenia school, believes that what motivated schools greatly to join and stay in the partnership was having the European partners on board (Interview, March 6th, 2019). Dr. Mamdouh, a mentor from university, expresses his great sense of commitment to the school he mentors. He continues to be very motivated even though due to management issues at his University and the novelty of joining international projects, he had not received any project remuneration. He continues to visit the school informally beyond the designated days for mentorship and meetings. He admitted to being fascinated with the concept of the PCL (Interview, February 24th, 2019). These were, of course, some of the significant examples of intrinsic motivation, there are of course other team members from university who are a lot more motivated by extrinsic factors such as project remuneration, promotion, and publication. Teachers, in general, manifested a lot more intrinsic motivation and a very large number of them described how the partnership and the mentorship they received resulted in visible student improvement of learning, greater attendance and even better achievement scores.

Teachers from the Sunflower school were very eager to describe the *impact the partnership had on students*. Students claimed that they were now a great deal more engaged in their learning. They create their own projects and conduct research. According to the teachers, student absence had greatly decreased and their attendance had risen due to the new teaching practices including active learning and role play. Teachers were also using innovative strategies to further engage students in the management of activities in the school such as the school broadcasting and morning lines. Students were engaged in the school's improvement plan. Students were even engaged in teaching their peers during formal classes. Many of the students now aspired to be teachers. This school came first in the whole district in terms of developing student leadership, creativity and capacity to teach. The school teachers conducted a survey at school where they asked the students about their level of satisfaction and students were now expressing happiness at being in school. Moreover, the students were now able to reflect and evaluate their teachers' performance. We actually met some of the students engaged in research and projects and one of them had been awarded a research scholarship in the USA (Focus Group Discussion, March 16th, 2019). We were able to obtain the end of year cumulative official scores for the second preparatory grade and the school had consistently been doing well for three consecutive academic years despite the increase in student activities and community outreach.

Having students teach in classes was not particular to the Sunflower school. Teachers in the Rose school

also explained how they developed this initiative of the "young student teacher". They also described all the research activities that were led by students. Some had researched Nano technology-related topics, others were researching the concept of freedom and yet another team was researching the political economy of the Islamic State (February 20th, 2019). Teachers from the Orchid school explained how their students were now involved in recycling activities and projects (Focus Group Discussion, March 17th, 2019).

Teachers from most schools asserted that student achievement had improved. We were able to exceptionally obtain comparative scores from two schools in Alexandria spanning three years with the start date of the project and the end date representing the current before the last year of the project. In the first case, the results pertained to the preparatory levels one and two, in the Gardenia school. The school showed consistent good results and good scores with slight improvements during the second year of implementation 2017/2018 in social studies and science for the first preparatory year and in all subjects for the second preparatory year. As for the Iris school, the scores for the fourth primary grade had notably improved in Arabic, English, Social Studies and dramatically improved in science. The only decline in grades was in religious studies and specifically Islamic religion. We believe this is an area where more work needs to be done. We do, however, have sufficient indicators for now to show the potential these partnerships have for improving student achievement.

A Day in the Jasmin Professional Development School by the PI of the project on March 11, 2019

As I walked into the very large school early in the morning, I was met by a friendly smiling headmaster who seemed to know the names of most of the children he met on his way. The children seemed very comfortable with the headmaster running towards him to get a morning greeting, hug or pet. The KG children had prepared a small play in the courtyard, where they created a small garden with flowers they had made themselves. The little boys in the play were trying to pick up the flowers and ruin the garden, while the girls were trying to prevent them by explaining the damage to nature. The purpose of the play was to highlight what they had learned around sustainable development and also it had a gender dimension.

I was later invited to attend a session organized by a group of young students who call themselves TEAM. These were a group of five who had prepared an amazing awareness session for their peers in school around the importance of having a goal and aim in life that one must attempt to achieve. They had researched the topic and used many interesting learning aids including audio-visual ones to capture the attention of the other students. They were also seeking to visit other neighbouring schools to spread awareness. The TEAM members had created this activity after they had visited the University of Ain Shams and observed a similar activity by young club members.

During the next class visit, I was invited to a grade one class, where students were studying ants in a multidisciplinary way and also role-playing ants. They learned about ants biologically, but also discussed their cooperative behaviour and collaboration in general. The class teacher then initiated a discussion about cooperation and some little boys recounted how they helped their mothers cook and wash dishes. They asserted that cooperation was time-saving and more efficient.

During the break, in the teachers' common room, three grade ten girls were observed teaching and tutoring younger slow learners in Arabic, Math and Science. The teachers were watching them and giving support and guidance. Also, during the break, a Christian and Moslem boy fought in public with signs of discrimination. A class was quickly organized around the concept of citizenship with three teachers of different subject matter led the discussion in the presence of the two boys. We then slipped next door to a small performance rehearsal by the music teacher and a group of children performed a song in sign language. A discussion then ensued on special needs and differences. The children would like everyone to learn the sign language.

Mai, a prominent member of the PCL, a school mentor and one who has been a strong media ambassador for the partnership project, led an Arabic class in correct classical Arabic. Mai believes in the power of language. She is also a graduate student at the University of Ain Shams. During the class, Mai highlighted the importance of the different cultures in Egypt. She emphasized the significant values of Nubia to the joy of some of the children who came originally from there. Mai also created opportunities for child participation and active learning as the children constructed a play.

At the end of the day, we all met in the teachers' common room where Mai and her colleagues had a session with Dr. Salma the mentor from university. The atmosphere was a very warm and friendly one. Food and drinks were served. Teachers were very supportive of each other and collegial. Dr. Salma was very systematic and as she apparently does routinely, she asked the teachers to reflect on their teaching that day through a number of leading questions she had prepared. Later, Mai, who is the director of the quality assurance and training unit, started a discussion with Dr. Salma and the other colleagues to prepare for the next sessions in the school training unit. They also planned the logistics for the sessions along with the topics. Students were freely allowed into the room for hugs and the exchange of encouragement. Before I left, Mai offered me an invaluable gift which is her own written record of the partnership journey with photos and said "please come again often and send more people to visit us you just do not know what these visits mean to us."

All the culturally deep transformations and attitudinal changes require group solidarity and for those concerned with theories of change, particularly educational organizational change, the process of change takes time. Groups go through a process of undoing or what Kurt Lewin calls unfreezing norms and questioning those especially when reflecting on their feeling of frustration and dissatisfaction with current conditions. The group then moves to the change stage wherein with the help of others, new norms are established. Finally, in the refreeze stage the new norms are internalized and adopted as the groups' new way of life (Arnold, 2015). It can be very safely said that the changes and transformations occurring with the SUP4PCL partners were very real and fitted the criteria for marginal improvements in many domains. Furthermore, the transformations had occurred at more than one level of depth and clearly the participants, through group support, had gradually internalized those changes. It is also clear that these various new cultural norms, habits of mind and innovative practices reached the end target of all reforms namely the students. One observed and touched the impact it had on students in more than one way. This particular outcome deserves to be studied independently in future studies. Moreover, impact also needs to be traced by structural levels both at the national and institutional levels. At the national level, very big steps are being made through the partnership namely the signing of a Memorandum of understanding with two national line ministries and several protocol agreements with local educational districts. The concept of a school-university partnership is quickly spreading and many in the peer communities of learners' report encountering much demand when they meet with other schools beyond the partnership. Many are now ambassadors to the idea in the media and their own networks as they would like to see the idea spread. In addition, through existing channels of policy dialogue the project managed to establish the beginnings of an incentive system for university mentors, who at times were more extrinsically motivated, by altering the rules of promotion for faculty. Faculty members are now going to be given more points for joining international projects and for serving and doing research in schools. More needs to be done to further incentivize and support teacher learning and performance. As for the outcomes on the institutional level, some very meaningful results of this project have been the introduction of new syllabi for courses particularly on research in the undergraduate programs of University as well as the strengthening of international offices in all the partner universities towards increased internationalization. Finally, Peer Communities of learners (PCLs) are expanding at school and university.

Challenges, Conclusion and Way Forward

Challenges

Some of the challenges recurrently mentioned in the literature are structural, contextual and bureaucratic. With reference to the structural issues, it is clear that often times structures for collaboration are absent including physical structures such as spaces for meeting. This is particularly true of schools in Egypt and also at the university level some faculty do not meet regularly for seminars. Moreover, time is the most constraining factor with regard to both types of institutions. Finally, both institutions value very different types of achievements. Schools value most the amount of teaching and curriculum coverage achieved, while universities value research and publication most of all and often times not done collaboratively. Involvement of faculty in PDS projects is not considered as “academic endeavours”. Many of the challenges have to do with lack of recognition of the value of creating such symbiotic partnerships. This is not specific to Egypt but may be found in other contexts (Ambrose, Natale, Murphey, & Schumacher, 1999; Peters, 2002).

Other challenges have to do with governance, staffing, resources and funding including poor workplace conditions, lack of resources, and unsupportive management at the different levels (Bathmaker, & Avis, 2005). A significant challenge is having the resources to build the evidence for successful PDS initiatives over time both on the moral ethical and practical levels in order to convince policymakers and reformers of their viability as a cost-effective potent strategy (Abdal-Haq, 1998).

An obvious and hugely daunting challenge is, of course, that of time. Time is a challenge on very many levels. It is not only a finite resource for most, whether teachers or faculty members who have to struggle so hard to meet all their complex and oftentimes impossible commitments, but is also important for the achievement of deep and profound results. Transformation as we well know takes time. Even the standards created originally by the National Council for Accrediting Teacher Education NCATE have four stages before the partnership reaches maturity: beginning level, developing level, standard level when

policies are put in place and cooperation becomes the norm, and at lead level when advanced professional development is sustained and regenerative. H. Peel, B. Peel and Baker (2002) have in fact outlined even more stages towards reaching a mature partnership such that at first people are consumed with hostility, they then try to build mutual confidence as they try and counter the lack of trust. Slowly they move into a period of truce with equal participation, followed by a period of small successes to then reach a fifth stage of recognizing the mutual benefits of the partnership. There is then a time for relapse and regression and as new members join in, the process is delayed and requires renewal to finally reach the eighth stage of continued collaborative efforts (Arnold, 2015). The process of solidifying, let alone sustaining and institutionalizing partnerships, take time and quite a lot of energy and resources. Reporting success is not without obstacles as well.

Another set of challenges is the often accompanying tensions between the beliefs that are claimed to have been reached and the actual practices during the process and journey of creating partnerships. This may be due to a lack of awareness and weak reflections on individual and collective behaviours. During our field study, several such examples emerged. During visits and interviews in many instances, leaders and school principals claimed to be highly democratic, empowering and participatory when it was very clear from their behaviour that they were not and were indeed very authoritarian. Meanwhile, whilst many spoke about the egalitarian relationships that had emerged between university faculty and school teachers, the truth is that there were other sets of hierarchical relationships and behaviours within schools that were quite evident between regular teachers and teachers in schools who held a Ph.D.

Another important challenge was that teachers were not given official recognition, encouragement and time to engage in CPD. Moreover, many of the teachers were pulled out of their schools and transferred to other schools. Some even taught in more than one school. The overload was huge.

Conclusion and The Way Forward

Using the four NCATE levels, our partnership is probably somewhere in the third level where some policies are in place but more needs to be done to make PDS more sustainable and regenerative. Clearly, the PDS participants seem to be performing well and are more focused on their students. Their time management has improved and their capacity to reflect is strengthened. Teachers and faculty have stronger and better relations with students and their pedagogies have much improved. University partners have a greater understanding of the work of teachers and have become involved in more meaningful reflection on their teaching and learning. Greater professional growth was perceived amongst teachers and collaboration is slowly becoming the norm. Stereotypes of teaching and teachers are being questioned and changed. New concepts and themes are being introduced such as inclusion, Global Citizenship, STEAM and Sustainable Development. Mentorship is an effective part of teacher and faculty growth, empowerment and retention (Snow, Flynn, Whisenand, & Mohr, 2016).

A fundamental recommendation is to mainstream and deepen the institutional presence of school-university partnerships to ensure sustainability. In many parts of the world, school-university partnerships are supported by legal frameworks and official documents. In Hong Kong, school-university partnerships were endorsed by a major government document. Many initiatives are government-funded and initiated. In the USA, the Holmes group was a consortium of large universities offering teacher education. In the UK and Wales, school-university partnerships were formally established in the nineties and were introduced as a national statutory requirement for initial teacher education (NG & Chan, 2012).

Furthermore, school-university partnerships need to expand to include as many stakeholders as possible such as other faculties/disciplines, students, the teaching profession and the practice field, international and national institutions, community schools, parent education programs, policymakers and most certainly civil society (Smith, 2016). Most importantly school-university partnerships need to develop district models where the partnership between the university is one that is fostered with a whole district. This was actually a demand made by several of the teachers participating in the current partnership and in particular the mentor from the Jasmin school mentioned in the vignette on page 65.

What is most needed is to witness a transition from what some have called first-order change to second-order change (Ross, et al., 1999). What this means basically is not stopping at making what exists more efficient as a result of the partnership, but making bolder structural transformations around school-university partnerships and Professional Development Schools so that new roles, behaviours and goals emerge for those participating in the partnership. Moreover, these new transformations need to be supported by policies and structures. Policymakers need to revisit existing structures in both institutions entering the partnership as well as the reward systems. Suggestions in that direction have already been presented to the Egyptian authorities. An official document was presented to several relevant committees outlining the structures, workload releases and incentives proposed as follows:

With regard to legal frameworks and structures, it was proposed that a law be enforced to oblige universities and the Ministry of Education to set up Professional Development Schools. In addition, it was suggested that universities and schools establish internal rules to encourage the formation of Peer Communities of Learners. Time spent in those activities would be regarded as official work time for both teachers and faculty. Having a partnership with a professional development school is to become a prerequisite for faculty accreditation by the National Agency for Quality Assurance and Accreditation in Education. Finally, an important component was the establishment of a national structure that would coordinate and oversee the formation of such partnerships as well as monitor and evaluate their evolution.

In order to incentivize school-university partnership at the university level the project suggested the following faculty policies and practices:

- Promotion of faculty should be based on higher weightings for community service and mentorship of school teachers. This would respond to the need for extrinsic motivation amongst some of the university faculty.
- Contrary to current practices, collaborative research should be given higher points in assessing the dossier for promotion and tenure. Currently, collaborative research is not high in the promotion evaluation system

in national universities.

- More weight needs to be placed for action research and research leading to school improvement.
- The dossier for promotion should contain evidence of participation in peer communities of learners as a way of making the time and effort spent worthwhile.
- Practitioners should be invited and encouraged to lecture at university. This seemed to work as a strong incentive amongst the teachers in the SUP4PCL partnership and it seemed to greatly motivate them to sustain the partnership and do better in school.
- Universities should be able to offer outstanding practitioners honorary diplomas.
- Faculties and schools of education going through reforms should invite school practitioners to be part of the process.
- Mentorship should constitute part of the offerings by faculties of education. Mentorship has proven to work quite well for the school teachers joining the SUP4PCL project and was recognized as a good strategy for lifelong learning and for improving teaching and learning in schools, but also in university.
- Faculty members engaged in school university partnerships should be getting a reduced teaching load. All faculty members in the project complained about overload and the scarcity of time available to support such initiatives.
- Faculties of education should establish technology labs for teacher professional development. The labs had apparently worked quite well for mentoring teachers and were also very instrumental for expanding the initiative through school clustering.
- The Ministry of Education should have a continuous professional development (CPD) policy that reinforces the formation of peer communities of learners (PCLs). Some were suggesting that this needed to be mandatory.
- The training and quality assurance units in each school should oversee and support the formation of PCLs. The project had greatly strengthened and empowered the quality assurance and training units and given them a new role that needs to be maintained. Their activities were made that much more effective through the existence of Peer Communities of Learners.
- Schools should make time and space available for the activation of Continuous Professional Development (CPD) and the meetings of the PCLs. This was not only the views of the authors of this case study and the coordination leadership of the project, International good practices but was also the prevailing views of almost all the teachers interviewed. They needed the time and space to meet as very often this was a great challenge and the benefits they got out of meeting regularly and learning collaboratively were clearly significant.
- University should support and strengthen school mentorship and the training units. All teachers in the project were clearly very grateful for the opportunity they were given to connect with the university, be mentored by faculty, learn new methods, ideas and practices.

In order to incentivize school-university partnership at the school level the project suggested the following policies and practices:

It must be emphasized that all the suggested policies and ideas for the sustainability of the partnership are not only widely shared by the participants in the initiative, from both schools and universities, but also other stakeholders such as the various committees on education in the Supreme Council of Universities SCU. This is particularly important for the sake of ensuring that when we do borrow concepts and practices from other regions and societies that they are not completely taken out of context (Zaalouk, 2013). More stakeholder conversations are extremely necessary in order to make the right policy choices. During many of the meetings with the project consortium when ideas were discussed on the way forward it was often suggested that perhaps in the case of Egypt what would work best was to enact clear cut directives on the establishment of Peer Communities of learners and the participation therein as preconditions for promotions. Many believed that following the Asian path may be best suited for the Egyptian context. A final conference is planned in March for the presentation of the results of the initiative in the presence of key policymakers and other stakeholders. A whole day is devoted to policy dialogue, a press conference and the way forward. The conference in March 2020 will not only serve as a conduit for dissemination but will, in fact, be regarded as an intervention to allow the different views on the way forward to surface as guidance for the necessary policy formulations.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Research Framework

Research Questions	Roles
RQ 1: What is the nature of the partnership in the project?	AUC
RQ 2: How does the SUP enhance the development of PCLs at university level?	Twinning FoEs
RQ 2: How does the SUP enhance the development of PCLs at school level?	EG FoEs
RQ 3: How has the PCL impacted on the transformation of professional learning practice at the university level?	Twinning FoEs
RQ 3: How has the PCL impacted on the transformation of professional learning practice at the school level?	EG FoEs
RQ 4: How does the SUP impact on beliefs, values and attitudes?	AUC
RQ 5: What are some of the tensions between beliefs/values and practice?	All

Appendix 2: Habits of Mind Questionnaire

الجامعة الأمريكية بالقاهرة
معهد الشرق الأوسط للتعليم العالي

استبانة الإتجاهات نحو التنمية المهنية

الأستاذ الفاضل/ الأستاذة الفاضلة

أعدت الاستبانة التالية للتعرف على رؤيتك حول بعض عناصر التنمية المهنية.

تتضمن الاستبانة (72) عبارة والمطلوب منك التفضل بقراءة كل من تلك العبارات بدقة وتحديد مدى موافقتك أو عدم موافقتك عليها وذلك بوضع علامة (√) أمامها تحت المربع الذي يعبر عن رأيك.

علما بأنه لا توجد إجابة صحيحة و أخرى خاطئة.

و لكل عبارة خمس إختيارات: (أوافق بشدة - أوافق - غير موافق - غير موافق بشدة).

وإن قدر تعاونك، يرجى الإحاطة أن النتائج المترتبة على تطبيق الاستبانة سوف تستخدم لأغراض البحث العلمي فقط، وسوف تعامل جميع المعلومات الواردة بسرية تامة.

غير موافق بشدة	غير موافق	أوافق	أوافق بشدة	العبارة	
				عند الانتهاء من عمل ما أراجع الخطوات و أقيم أدائي.	1
				أفضل النقاش مع الإثنث عن الذكور حيث لديهم نزعة أقوى نحو التسامح و التوافق.	2
				يمكنني تغيير شكل جلوس الطالب داخل الفصل الدراسي	3
				أهم ما ينبغي أن يتعلمه الطالب محتوى المواد الدراسية المقررة	4
				عند تلقى نقد يفضل عدم المواجهة و تجنب الموقف.	5
				لا يجوز وجود أكثر من قائد في أى عمل.	6
				أستطيع إجراء إجتماع مع أولياء الأمور.	7
				يجب أن يساعد المعلم كل تلميذ على أن ينمو حسب سرعته في التعلم.	8
				لا يجوز إعطاء نفس قدر الإهتمام عند الإستماع لأطراف مناقشة أو مناقشة	9
				أستطيع الإسهام في تنفيذ خطة برنامج التنمية المهنية في مؤسستي.	10
				بإمكان الطلبة الإسهام في حل مشكلات المؤسسة التعليمية.	11
				الصداقة بين الطلاب و المعلمين تقلل هيبه المعلمين و إحترامهم.	12
				عند تكلفني بمهام لا تلائم قدراتي فيفضل ترشيح شخص آخر.	13
				التحصيل و التعلم هما وسيلتان للحصول على وظيفة في المستقبل.	14
				لدي القدرة على التأثير على القرارات الهامة المرتبطة بالقيادة المؤسسية.	15
				خطة الدرس يجب أن تكون لجميع الطلبة وفق معايير موحدة	16
				في معظم الأحيان أفضل إنجاز العمل بشكل فردي.	17
				يمكنني استخدام وسائل مختلفة لتقييم الطلاب مثل ملف إنجاز الطالب.	18
				البحث العلمي هو في الأساس عمل أكاديمي يقوم به متخصصون.	19
				إنهاء القيام بعمل ما أراجع الخطوات و أقيم أدائي.	20
				المعلم يجب أن يلم بالسياسات التربوية والقواعد والقوانين والهيكل التنظيمية.	21
				النقد يقصد الإنسان نقده بذاته.	22
				الشدة مطلوبة في تربية المتعلمين.	23

1 MEIHE - AUC

24	الكتابة الحرة حول الأداءات المهنية ترف لمن لديه موهبة الكتابة.
25	كثير من الأمور الخاصة بطرق التدريس لا تستدعي التقصي و الفحص.
26	تقييم عمل الطلاب يجب ان يتم بالمقارنة مع أداء أقرانهم بالصف.
27	عندما أواجه رأي مغاير لرأي أفضل الإبتعاد عن الموقف.
28	عند قراءة آراء متباينة حول معلومة ما، أقوم بعملية تفضيل وفق المنطق العام.
29	يمكنني الإسهام في التخطيط لمحتوى أنشطة التنمية المهنية في مؤسستي.
30	أرحب بمساعدة غيري من المعلمين حتى او تتطلب ذلك بقائي بعد انتهاء اليوم الدراسي.
31	تميل الإتبات إلى نقد الآخرين أكثر من الرجال.
32	قبل الشروع في القيام بعمل ما أراجع الخطوات التي يجب عملها.
33	من الصعب قيادة فريق يعبر عن آرائه بحرية.
34	أفضل الطرق لقياس أداء الطلاب تتم بمتابعة تطور أدائه الشخصي.
35	أستطيع أن أدخل عادات جديدة في شكل التفاعل داخل الفصل مثل تشكيل العمل في مجموعات صغيرة.
36	الإختلاف في الآراء يضع الجيد و الوقت.
37	لا يجب الوقوف عند الرأي الصائر من أشخاص غير متخصصين.
38	وأقتصر التعلم على الطلاب.
39	أستطيع المعلم مناقشة القواعد و النواتج التربوية.
40	في كثير من الأحيان ينبع النقد من موقف عدائي ما.
41	من أهم مؤشرات نجاح المؤسسة أن يكون لدى خريجها رغبة شديدة للتعلم المستمر.
42	هناك مجالات فلسفية و حيالية لا يفضل الدخول في مناقشات حولها.
43	اجتماعات إدارة المؤسسة مع العاملين تهدر وقت اليوم الدراسي.
44	يعتمد التعلم على الكتاب فقط.
45	نتأى حلول مشاكل المؤسسة التعليمية من قبل الوزارة فقط.
46	عندما يتطلب الأمر لابد من مواجهة الزملاء بعبوب شخصياتهم.
47	إكتساب مهارات البحث لا يتم إلا من خلال دراسات متخصصة في الجامعات.
48	الإختبارات التحصيلية هي أفضل الطرق لقياس نواتج التعلم.
49	أستطيع أن أجنّب الطلاب من خلال التواصل الإجتماعي.
50	عند الإنصات للأخر أحرص على إستخلاص ما إستوعبته من حديثه.
51	يفضل أن يتقبل المعلم نقد الطلاب له.
52	يمكنني مع زملائي وضع برنامج متكامل لأنشطة دورية للتنمية المهنية.
53	العمل الجماعي يعيق التقييم الفردي للطلاب.
54	يمكنني أن أطالب المؤسسة التعليمية بعقد إجتماع عام حول موضوع شديد الأهمية.
55	من الصعب الوصول إلى توافق إذا كان هناك إختلاف حول المبادئ.
56	يشيب الحوار في ضياع الوقت.

Handwritten signature in Arabic script.

57	من المهم أن يدعم المعلمون بعضهم البعض في التصدي للسياسات واللوائح الجديدة.
58	الفريق الناجح هو ذلك الفريق الذي يضم أفراد متقاربين الرأي.
59	استطيع مشاركة غيري من المعلمين في أنشطة لتحسين المؤسسة.
60	عند تلقى نقد متكرر من أعضاء فريق العمل من المفيد بناء فريق آخر.
61	يمكنني إجراء بحوث في إطار صلي بالمؤسسة.
62	من أهم مخرجات التعلم معرفة المتعلم ولجبات المواطنة و حقوقها.
63	الاجتماع الشهري لجميع العاملين يضيع الوقت.
64	أحرص على المشاركة في تحسين الأنشطة المؤسسية حتى بعد إنتهاء اليوم الدراسي.
65	إذا تطلب الأمر مواجهة عضو الفريق بأمر محرج و لكن مفيد للعمل، يجب مواجهته بوضوح.
66	يجب أن يستفيد المعلم من تقييم الطلاب له.
67	عند الإستماع للآخر تتكون لدينا آراء مخالفة.
68	استطيع بناء فريق يحظى داخل المؤسسة لدراسة مشكلاتها.
69	يحرص المعلم المتميز على تنمية روح الفريق داخل الصف.
70	أحرص على الإضلاع باستمرار على البحوث التربوية في تخصصي.
71	يسهم التعاون مع المعلمين في إيجاد بيئة تعليمية يشعر فيها الطلاب بالرضا عن أنفسهم.
72	أفضل ثقافة التعاون داخل الصف عن التنافس.

Appendix 3: Focus Group Discussion Questions

الهيكـل (أو البنية)

Structure

- 1- ما هو الهدف الأساسي لاجتماعاتكم في مجتمعات التعلم ؟
What has been the primordial purpose of your meetings?
- 2- من يقوم بتحديد الهدف ؟
Who decides for purpose?
- 3- كيف يتم اتخاذ القرارات بخصوص منهجية العمل المتعلقة بمجتمعات التعلم داخل الشراكة ؟
How are decisions made concerning processes of work pertaining to the partnership examples?
- 4- كيف يتم التعبير عن الالتزام بالشراكة بين المدرسة والجامعة ؟
How is commitment to the partnership expressed?
- 5- ما هو الدليل على الانتماء إلى مجتمع التعلم ؟
What evidence shows belongingness to the community/groups?
- 6- ما هو معدل تكرار الاجتماعات ؟
What are the frequencies of meetings?

الإجراء \ أو المنهجية

Process

- 7- ما هي المواضيع أو الأنشطة المطروحة خلال اجتماعات مجتمعات التعلم للأقران ؟
What topics or activities that take place during your PCL meetings?
- 8- ما هي الأدلة التي تدعم الثقة والاحترام والتقارب ؟
What evidence is there to support trust, respect and closeness?
- 9- كيف يتم تبادل المعرفة في مجتمع التعلم للأقران ؟ وهل يوجد معرفة جديدة مضافة ؟
How does knowledge exchange/transfer take place in the PCL and is there new knowledge added?
- 10- ما هي الأدلة على منح فرص متكافئة للتعلم مدى الحياة في مجتمع التعلم للأقران المنتمون إليه أو في مؤسساتكم ؟
What evidence is there for providing equal opportunities for LLL in your PCL and institutions?
- 11- لأي درجة تتم مناقشة مواضيع حول التربية العملية ؟
To what extent do you discuss issues around practitioners?
- 12- لأي مدى تتم مناقشة مواضيع حول البحث والاستقصاء ؟
To what extent do you discuss issues around research and inquiry?

النتائج \ التأثير

Outcomes/Impact

13- كنتاج لهذه الشراكة لأي مدى تشعر بالتجدد والتمكين؟

To what extent did you feel renewed and/or empowered by virtue of this partnership?

14- ما هي التطورات الجانبية التي يمكنك أن تصفها؟

What marginal improvements can you depict?

15- ما هي الشراكات الهيكلية التي تبنيها مع كليتي الفن والعلوم؟

What partnerships with structures are you building with faculties of arts and science?

16- ما هي التحديات التي واجهتكم؟ كيف يتم التصدي لها؟

What challenges did you face? How were they addressed?

Appendix 4: Interview Questions

Dear participant,

We are extremely honoured to have you as part of this project entitled School and University Partnerships for Peer Communities of Learners. We believe that through our combined efforts we will contribute to the transformation of the quality of teaching and learning in our various countries. The following tool requires that you carefully disclose how your participation in this project might have had an impact on the development of peer communities of learners (PCL) in your educational institution and how these PCLs in turn might have supported the transformation of your professional learning practice.

Please rest assured that your responses will be confidential and will only be used for research purposes. Feel free to write openly and elaborately.

Thanking you for your kind collaboration

Demographic information:

Gender: Female Male

Age: 20-30 31-40 41-50 Above 51

Date of joining the project: Month _____ Year _____

Area of specialization: _____

Years of experience: _____

Nature of the educational Institution: School University

السادة المشاركون،

يشرفنا وجودكم و مشاركتكم معنا في هذ المشروع "الشراكة بين الجامعة والمدرسة لبناء مجتمعا الأقران من المتعلمين"

نحن نؤمن أن من خلال جهودنا المشتركة سوف نصل إلى الارتقاء بجودة التعليم والتعلم في بلادنا. هذه الأداة المرفقة تتطلب من سيادتكم الإفصاح عن أثر مشاركتكم في هذا المشروع في بناء وتكوين مجتمعات التعلم بين الأقران في مؤسساتكم التعليمية. كما تقيس الأداة أثر انتمائكم لهذه المجتمعات على أدائكم المهني. نؤكد لحضراتكم أن جميع الإجابات سوف تظل سرية ولن تستخدم إلا لأغراض البحث العلمي.

برجاء الاستفاضة في الإجابة على الأسئلة بشكل واضح و صريح.

شاكرين لكم حسن تعاونكم

بيانات أساسية:

النوع : ذكر أنثى

الفئة العمرية : ٣٠-٢٠ عاما ٤٠-٣١ عاما ٥٠-٤١ عاما ٥١ عاما أو أكثر

تاريخ الالتحاق بالمشروع : شهر _____ سنة _____

التخصص: _____

سنوات الخبرة: _____

طبيعة المؤسسة التعليمية : مدرسة جامعة

- 1) Which events and seminars did you participate in during the life of the project?
الرجاء ذكر الأنشطة والاجتماعات واللقاءات التي شاركتم فيها خلال عمر هذا المشروع
- 2) To what extent did you feel renewed and/or empowered by virtue of this partnership?
لأي مدى تشعر بالتجدد والتمكين كنتاج للشراكة بين المدرسة والجامعة؟
- 3) Do you practice regular reflection? how often and what is your preferred mode of reflection?
هل تقوم بالتفكير التأمل بانتظام؟ كم مرة؟ وما هو الأسلوب المفضل لديك للتفكير؟
- 4) How has reflection during your participation in the project impacted on your learning?
برجاء وصف أثر عمليات التفكير و التأمل اثناء مشاركتكم في المشروع على تعلمكم
- 5) To what extent do you feel you have become an agent of change?
إلى أي مدى تشعر بأنك أصبحت محرك للتغيير؟
- 6) What are your individual goals? And how have they changed as a result of the partnership?
ما هي أهدافك الفردية؟ وكيف تغيرت تلك الأهداف كنتاج للشراكة؟
- 7) Has this experience given you a sense of belonging and how has your professional identity changed?
هل منحتك هذه التجربة إحساس بالانتماء؟ وكيف تغيرت هويتك المهنية؟
- 8) Please describe the various peer communities of learners that you belong to?
برجاء ذكر أنواع مجتمعات التعلم بين الأقران اللآني تنتمون إليها.
- 9) To what extent do you identify with the community of professionals at your workplace and how is this manifested?
إلى أي مدى لديكم شعور بالانتماء نحو مجتمع التعلم في مكان العمل؟ وكيف يتم التعبير عن ذلك؟
- 10) To what extent do you identify with the community of professionals beyond your workplace and how is this manifested?
إلى أي مدى لديكم شعور بالانتماء نحو مجتمع التعلم في مكان خارج نطاق العمل؟ وكيف يتم التعبير عن ذلك؟
- 11) To what extent has the professional support gained in this project been useful and how?
إلى أي مدى كانت هناك استفادة من الدعم و الإرشاد التربوي في ممارساتكم المهنية؟
- 12) Do you now practice collaborative teaching?
هل تمارس الآن التدريس التعاوني؟
- 13) What joint projects and programs are you engaged in currently?
ما هي المشاريع و البرامج الأخرى المشترك فيها حاليا؟
- 14) What joint projects and programs are you planning for as a result of the partnership?
ما هي المشاريع أو البرامج الأخرى التي تخططون لها كنتيجة للشراكة؟
- 15) Please describe what changes/ developments, if any, that have occurred to your teaching approaches since joining the project?
برجاء وصف التغييرات التي طرأت على أسلوبكم في التدريس منذ مشاركتكم في هذا المشروع

16) What marginal improvements can you already depict in the following domains?

ما هي التطورات الجانبية التي يمكنك أن تصفها في المجالات التالية؟

A) In what ways has your organization of teaching changed as a result of this project? Please give examples

كيف تم تغيير أسلوب التخطيط للتدريس نتيجة لمشاركتكم في المشروع ، برجاء إعطاء بعض الأمثلة

B) In what ways has the presentation of your content changed as a result of this project? Please give examples

كيف تم تغيير أسلوب عرض المحتوي العلمي أثناء التدريس نتيجة لمشاركتكم في المشروع؟، برجاء إعطاء بعض الأمثلة

C) In what ways has your classroom instruction changed as a result of this project? Please give examples

كيف تم تغيير طرق التدريس داخل الصف الدراسي نتيجة لمشاركتكم في المشروع؟ برجاء إعطاء بعض الأمثلة

D) In what ways has your interaction with students changed as a result of this project? Please give examples

كيف تم تغيير أسلوب تفاعلكم مع الطلاب نتيجة لمشاركتكم في المشروع؟ برجاء إعطاء بعض الأمثلة

17) To what extent do you employ digital applications and tools in your teaching and learning as a result of this project? Please give examples

إلى أي مدى يتم استخدام تكنولوجيا التعليم في التدريس والتعلم الذاتي منذ مشاركتكم في المشروع؟ برجاء إعطاء بعض الأمثلة

18) What are identified gaps between aspired to practice and actual practice? Please give examples

يرجي توضيح الفجوات بين تصوراتكم في الممارسات التربوية المثلى و قدرتكم على تطبيقها. برجاء إعطاء بعض الأمثلة

19) In Conclusion, we would like you to order the following domains of learning in accordance to their impact upon yourselves during your participation in the project. Please prioritize in ascending order. (i.e. the most important gets 1, and the least important gets 4).

- The self in learning and teaching
- Professional Identity
- Mentorship
- Teaching and practice

في نهاية هذه الأداة ، يرجى ترتيب مجالات التعلم أثناء مشاركتكم في المشروع وفق درجة الاستفادة. ويتم ترتيب المجالات تصاعديا أي أن رقم 1 يمثل أهم مجال ورقم 4 يمثل أقل مجال في الاستفادة والأهمية لديكم:

- النمو الذاتي في التدريس والتعلم
- الهوية المهنية.....
- الارشاد التربوي.....
- اساليب التدريس والممارسات المهنية.....

الجامعة الأمريكية بالقاهرة

استمارة موافقة مسبقة للمشاركة في دراسة بحثية

عنوان البحث : طبيعة الشراكة بين المدرسة و الجامعة ، خطواتها و الاثر الملموس

الباحث الرئيسي: ا.د ملك ز علوك
البريد الالكتروني: mz@aucegypt.edu
الهاتف: 01229911116

انت مدعو للمشاركة في دراسة بحثية عن طبيعة الشراكة بين المدرسة و الجامعة ، خطواتها و الاثر الملموس

هدف الدراسة هو احداث تطوير تربوي علي مستويين المدرسة و الجامعة

نتائج البحث ستنشر في دوريه متخصصه و مؤتمر علمي.

المدة المتوقعة للمشاركة في هذا البحث علي حد اقصي ساعتان من الزمن

اجراءات الدراسة تشمل على المشاركة ضمن المناقشات البورية الجماعية و المقابلات الفردية غير المقننة.

المخاطر المتوقعة لا توجد مخاطر أو مضايقات متوقعة من المشاركة في هذا البحث .

الاستفادة المتوقعة من المشاركة في البحث سوف تعطي فرصة إضافية للمشاركين في ممارسة اسلوب التفكير.

السرية واحترام الخصوصية: المعلومات التي ستدلى بها في هذا البحث سوف تكون سرية

أي أسئلة متعلقة بهذه الدراسة أو حقوق المشاركين فيها أو عند حدوث أي اصابات ناتجة عن هذه المشاركة يجب ان توجه الى ا.د ملك ز علوك ،
25611492

ان المشاركة في هذه الدراسة ماهي الا عمل تطوعي. حيث أن الامتناع عن المشاركة لا يتضمن أي عقوبات أو فقدان أي مزايا تحقق لك. ويمكنك
أيضا التوقف عن المشاركة في أي وقت من دون عقوبة أو فقدان لهذه المزايا.

الامضاء:

اسم المشارك :

التاريخ :/...../.....

To: Malak Zaalouk
Cc: Sherine Baher
From: Atta Gebril, Chair of the IRB
Date: Feb 6, 2019
Re: Approval of study

This is to inform you that I reviewed your research proposal entitled "Structure, process and outcomes of school university partnerships" and determined that it required consultation with the IRB under the "expedited" category. The proposal used appropriate procedures to minimize risks to human subjects and that adequate provision was made for confidentiality and data anonymity of participants in any published record. I believe you will also make adequate provision for obtaining informed consent of the participants.

This approval letter was issued under the assumption that you have not started data collection for your research project. Any data collected before receiving this letter could not be used since this is a violation of the IRB policy.

Please note that IRB approval does not automatically ensure approval by CAPMAS, an Egyptian government agency responsible for approving some types of off-campus research. CAPMAS issues are handled at AUC by the office of the University Counsellor, Dr. Ashraf Hatem. The IRB is not in a position to offer any opinion on CAPMAS issues, and takes no responsibility for obtaining CAPMAS approval.

This approval is valid for only one year. In case you have not finished data collection within a year, you need to apply for an extension.

Thank you and good luck.

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Atta Gebril".

Dr. Atta Gebril
IRB chair, The American University in Cairo
2046 HUSS Building
T: 02-26151919
Email: agebril@aucegypt.edu

قرار رئيس الجهاز المركزي للتعبئة العامة والإحصاء
بالتفويض

رقم (١١١٧) لسنة ٢٠١٩/٢٠١٨

في شأن قيام الباحثة / ملكة محمد الحسيني زعلوك - استاذة ممارس ومدير معهد الشرق الأوسط للتعليم العالي كلية الدراسات العليا في التربية / الجامعة الأمريكية بالقاهرة - بإجراء دراسة بحثية بعنوان: (طبيعة الشراكة بين المدرسة والجامعة "خطوتها والأثر الملموس") وذلك بهدف الترقى .

رئيس الجهاز

- بعد الإطلاع على القرار الجمهوري رقم (٢٩١٥) لسنة ١٩٦٤ بشأن إنشاء الجهاز المركزي للتعبئة العامة والإحصاء.
- وعلى قرار رئيس الجهاز رقم (٢٣١) لسنة ١٩٦٨ في شأن إجراء الإحصاءات والتعدادات والاستفتاءات والاستقصاءات.
- وعلى قرار رئيس الجهاز رقم (١٣١٤) لسنة ٢٠٠٧ بشأن التفويض في بعض الاختصاصات.
- وعلى كتاب الجامعة الأمريكية بالقاهرة - الوارد للجهاز في ٢٠١٩/١/٢٧ .

قـرـر

- مادة ١: تقوم الباحثة / ملكة محمد الحسيني زعلوك - استاذة ممارس ومدير معهد الشرق الأوسط للتعليم العالي كلية الدراسات العليا للتربية / الجامعة الأمريكية بالقاهرة - بإجراء الدراسة الميدانية المشار إليها عالية.
- مادة ٢: تجري الدراسة على عينة حجمها (١٨٥) مائة وخمسة وثلاثون مفردة من معلمي المدارس الملحقة بكليات التربية وكذا استاذة كليات التربية بالجامعات التالية: (عين شمس - الإسكندرية - طوان) .
- مادة ٣: تجمع البيانات اللازمة لهذه الدراسة بموجب الاستمارة المعدة لذلك وعدد صفحاتها ثلاث صفحات معتددة كل صفحة منها بخاتم الجهاز المركزي للتعبئة العامة والإحصاء.
- مادة ٤: تقوم الجامعات المستهدفة - وتحت إشراف السادة أمناء عموم تلك الجامعات - بتيسير إجراء هذه الدراسة الميدانية ومراعاة الضوابط الخاصة بتقييم درجة سرية البيانات والمعلومات المتداولة مسبقاً بمعرفة كل جهة طبقاً لما جاء بخطة الأمن بها.
- مادة ٥: يراعى موافقة مفردات العينة - وسرية البيانات الفردية طبقاً لقتون الجهاز رقم (٣٥) لسنة ١٩٦٠ والمعدل بالقتون رقم (٢٨) لسنة ١٩٨٢ وعدم استخدام البيانات التي يتم جمعها لأغراض أخرى غير أغراض هذه الدراسة .
- مادة ٦: يجري العمل الميداني خلال ستة أشهر من تاريخ صدور هذا القرار .
- مادة ٧: يوافق الجهاز المركزي للتعبئة العامة والإحصاء بنسخة من النتائج النهائية لهذه الدراسة.
- مادة ٨: ينفذ هذا القرار من تاريخ صدوره .
- صدر في: ٢٠١٩/١/٢٧

١١٢٩
مجدى محمد جواد
قائم بأعمال
مدير عام الإدارة العامة للأمن

قرار رئيس الجهاز المركزي للتعبئة العامة والإحصاء
بالتفويض

رقم (٤٥) لسنة ٢٠١٨

في شأن قيام الأستاذة الدكتورة / منك محمد الحسيني زغولك - المسجلة بمعهد الشرق الأوسط للتعليم المالي بالجامعة الأمريكية بالقاهرة - بإجراء دراسة ميدانية بعنوان (التحول في تصورات وقيم ومعارف المعلمين في المدارس المهنية وكليات التربية) وذلك بهدف الترقى

رئيس الجهاز

- بعد الإطلاع على القرار الجمهوري رقم (٢٩١٥) لسنة ١٩٦٤ بشأن إنشاء الجهاز المركزي للتعبئة العامة والإحصاء .
- وعلى قرار رئيس الجهاز رقم (٢٣١) لسنة ١٩٦٨ في شأن إجراء الإحصاءات والتعدادات والاستفتاءات والإستقصاءات.
- وعلى قرار رئيس الجهاز رقم (١٣١٤) لسنة ٢٠٠٧ بشأن التفويض في بعض الاختصاصات .
- وعلى كتاب الجامعة الأمريكية بالقاهرة / السوار: للجهاز في ٢٠١٨/ ٨/ ١٩ .

فصل

- مادة ١: تقوم الأستاذة الدكتورة / منك محمد الحسيني زغولك - المسجلة بمعهد الشرق الأوسط للتعليم العالي بالجامعة الأمريكية بالقاهرة - بإجراء الدراسة الميدانية المشار إليها عالياً .
- مادة ٢: تجري الدراسة علي عينة حجمها (٣٠٠) ثلاثمائة مفردة موزعة كالآتي :
- (١٥٠) مفردة من أعضاء هيئة التدريس بكليات التربية بالجامعات الآتية (عين شمس - دنوان الإسكندرية).
- (١٥٠) مفردة من مطمي المدارس المهنية (الملحقة بكليات التربية) بمحافظتي (الفاخرة والإسكندرية).
- مادة ٣: تجمع البيانات اللازمة لهذه الدراسة بموجب الاستمارة المعدة لذلك وعدد صفحاتها ثلاث صفحات معتمدة كل منها بخاتم الجهاز المركزي للتعبئة العامة والإحصاء .
- مادة ٤: تقوم الجامعات المستهدفة - وتحت إشراف السادة / أمناء عموم تلك الجامعات - بتيسير اجراء هذه الدراسة الميدانية - مع مراعاة الضوابط الخاصة بتقييم درجة سرية البيانات والمعلومات المتداوله مسبقا بمعرفة كل جهة طبقا لما جاء بخطة الامن بها.
- مادة ٥: يراعى موافقة مفردات العينة - وسرية البيانات الفردية طبقا لقانون الجهاز رقم (٣٥) لسنة ١٩٦٠ والمعدل بالقانون رقم (٢٨) لسنة ١٩٨٢ وعدم استخدام البيانات التي يتم جمعها لأغراض أخرى غير أغراض هذه الدراسة.

مادة ٦: يجري العمل الميداني خلال ثمانية أشهر من تاريخ صدور هذا القرار .

مادة ٧: يوافق الجهاز المركزي للتعبئة العامة والإحصاء بنسخة من النتائج النهائية لهذه الدراسة

مادة ٨: ينفذ هذا القرار من تاريخ صدوره .

صدر في: ٢٠١٨/٨/٢٦

محمد معلوح

مدير عام الإدارة العامة للأمن

Appendix 6: Alignment of FGD Questions with Structure and Process of the SU Partnership

Table		
<i>Alignment of FGD questions with structure and process of the SU partnership</i>		
	Structure	Process
1	How are decisions made concerning processes of work pertaining to the partnership examples?	What evidence is there to support trust, respect and closeness?
2	How is commitment to the partnership expressed	How does knowledge exchange/transfer take place in the PCL and is there new knowledge added?
3	What evidence shows a sense of belonging to the community/groups?	What evidence is there for providing equal opportunities for LLL in your PCL and institutions?
4	What are the frequencies of meetings?	What has been the primordial purpose of your meetings?
5	What topics or activities take place during PCL meetings (who makes decisions)	Who decides for purpose?
7		To what extent do you discuss issues around practitioners?
8		To what extent do you discuss issues around research and inquiry?

Appendix 7: Alignment of FGD Questions with the Impact of the SU Partnership

Table <i>Alignment of FGD questions with the impact of the SU partnership</i>			
Impact	Title	Main question	FGD question
Impact 1	“The self in Teaching and Learning”	How self-reflection and the acquired learning philosophy impact on teaching and learning	To what extent did you feel renewed and/or empowered by virtue of this partnership?
Impact 2	Professional identity, value and development in teaching and learning”	How professional identity articulates itself within learning communities across borders	NA
Impact 3	“Professional communication and dialogue in teaching and learning”	How professionals are able to collaborate in research, teaching and learning	What partnerships with structures are you building with faculties of arts and science?
Impact 4	“Professional knowledge of skills in teaching and learning”	This refers to the skills and pedagogies employed by professionals to plan for and manage the classrooms	What marginal improvements can you depict?
Impact 5	“Personal and professional digital capacity in teaching and learning”	This refers to the awareness gained by professionals on the digital possibilities and the ability to apply in accordance to identified gaps and challenges	NA

Appendix 8: Alignment of Interview Questions with Impact from the SU Partnership

Table <i>Alignment of interview questions with impact from the SU partnership</i>			
Impact	Title	Main question	Interview question
Impact 1	“The self in Teaching and Learning”	How self-reflection and the acquired learning philosophy impact on teaching and learning	How has reflection during your participation in the project impacted your learning?
Impact 2	Professional identity, value and development in teaching and learning”	How professional identity articulates itself within learning communities across borders	<p>Please describe the various peer communities of learners that you belong to?</p> <p>To what extent do you identify with the community of professionals at your workplace and how is this manifested?</p> <p>To what extent do you identify with the community of professionals beyond your workplace and how is this manifested?</p>
Impact 3	“Professional communication and dialogue in teaching and learning”	How professionals are able to collaborate in research, teaching, and learning	To what extent has the professional support gained in this project partnership been useful and how?
Impact 4	“Professional knowledge of skills in teaching and learning”	This refers to the skills and pedagogies employed by professionals to plan for and manage the classrooms	<p>Please describe what changes/ developments, if any, that have occurred to your teaching approaches since joining the project?</p> <p>In what ways has your organization of teaching changed as a result of this project? Please give examples</p> <p>In what ways has the presentation of your content changed as a result of this project? Please give examples</p> <p>In what ways has your classroom instruction changed as a result of this project? Please give examples</p> <p>In what ways has your interaction with students changed as a result of this project? Please give examples</p>
Impact 5	“Personal and professional digital capacity in teaching and learning”	This refers to the awareness gained by professionals on the digital possibilities and the ability to apply in accordance to identified gaps and challenges	<p>To what extent do you employ digital applications and tools in your teaching and learning as a result of this project? Please give examples</p> <p>What are identified gaps between aspired to practice and actual practice? Please give examples</p>

Appendix 9: The Signed MOU with the MOETE and MOHE

مذكرة تفاهم

بين وزارة التربية والتعليم والتعليم الفني ومقرها : 12 شارع الفلكي، الإنشاس والمنيرة، السيدة زينب، محافظة القاهرة ويمثلها السيد الوزير/ أ.د. طارق شوقي

وزير التربية والتعليم والتعليم الفني

ووزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي ومقرها : 101 ش قصر العينى، قصر العينى، السيدة زينب، محافظة القاهرة ويمثلها السيد الوزير/ أ.د. خالد عبد الغفار

وزير التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي

ومعهد الشرق الأوسط للتعليم العالي بالجامعة الأمريكية ومقرها : طريق الجامعة الأمريكية، شارع التسعين، القاهرة الجديدة ويمثلها الأستاذ الدكتور إيهاب عيد الرحمن

الرئيس الأكاديمي للجامعة الأمريكية

تمهيد:

يقود معهد الشرق الأوسط للتعليم العالي بالجامعة الأمريكية - من خلال المشروع الممول من قبل الإتحاد الأوربي ERASMUS+ - مبادرة حول الشراكة بين المدارس والجامعات لبناء مجتمعات معرفة، وهي مبادرة لتطوير كليات التربية وبعض المدارس النظامية في أن واحد. وتقوم هذه المبادرة على إلحاق بعض المدارس النظامية بكليات التربية وهي ظاهرة نجحت بقوة في مصر سابقا وفي العديد من البلدان المتقدمة وقد سميت هذه المدارس بالمدارس المهنية نسبة إلى إسهامها الواضح في التنمية المهنية لدى التربويين. فقد ظهرت هذه المدارس في بدايات القرن الماضى وازدهرت في التسعينات من القرن لتكون مجتمعات التعلم وتضمن الجودة في التعليم من خلال التعاون والتكامل بين المدرسة والجامعة وتلبى هذه المبادرة إحتياجات المتعلمين والتربويين في التأهيل والتطوير.

البند الاول

يعتبر التمهيد السابق جزء لا يتجزأ من مذكرة التفاهم ومكملا ومتمماً له ولأحكامها

البند الثاني

الاهداف العامة

1. يهدف المشروع الاوربي الذى يقوده معهد الشرق الاوسط الى الحاق ٤٥ مدرسة نظاميه بثلاث كليات تربيه هي عين شمس، الإسكندرية، وحلوان وفق المعايير الآتية:
 - المدارس العامة
 - المدارس المجاورة
 - المدارس التى لديها وحدة ضمان الجودة
 - المدارس التى لديها الرغبة فى المشاركة
 - المدارس التى لديها البنية التحتية التكنولوجية.

كما يهدف المشروع إلى المساهمة فى تطوير هذه المدارس من خلال الدعم الفنى المستمر بالإضافة إلى بناء قدرات وحدات الجودة داخل هذه المدارس بالمعدات التى تمكنهم من القيام بأدوارهم وتعتبر هذه المبادرة جزءاً لا يتجزأ من المبادرة الوطنية لتطوير كليات التربية التى تقودها لجنة التخطيط بالقطاع التربوى بالمجلس الأعلى للجامعات إذ أن المدارس الملحقة بالجامعات جزء أصيل من النقاط الرئيسة التى تشكل رؤية التطوير.

البند الثالث

نطاق التنفيذ والجهات المستهدفة

تنفذ المبادرة على مدار ثلاث سنوات و سوف تبدأ فى السنة الأولى بالحاق ١٥ مدرسة، بموجب ٥ مدارس لكل من الثلاث كليات، ثم تتوسع الدائرة من خلال التشبيك مع مدارس أخرى حتى تصل إلى عدد ٤٥ مدرسة بنهاية الثلاث سنوات. سوف يبدأ المشروع بدراسات لكل المدارس فى المرحلة الأولى لتحديد الاحتياجات و الوقوف على الوضع الراهن قبل البدء فى الدعم الفنى.

سوف يبدأ الدعم الفنى فى السنة الأولى من خلال حقيبة بحوث الفعل ARAS التى تتضمن أنشطة حول الإرشاد التربوى و بناء مجتمعات المعرفة. وقد تم إعتقاد الحقيقة فى الأكاديمية المهنية للمعلمين عام ٢٠١٥. أما فى المراحل التالية للمشروع فسوف يقوم الفريق ببناء و تطوير مواد تدريبية وإرشادية أخرى وفق الإحتياج التى سوف تعتمدها الأكاديمية المهنية بدورها وتنشرها الوزارة كيفما شاءت.

وبناء عليه وإيماناً بأهمية الشراكة بين التعليم العالي والتعليم ما قبل الجامعي، وإتساقاً مع التواصل والتكامل بين تطوير كليات التربية وتطوير المدارس على أسس بحثية وعلمية وإدراكاً لمحورية أداء المعلمين، إتفقت وزارة التربية والتعليم والتعليم الفني (طرف أول)، ووزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي (طرف ثاني) على إبرام مذكرة تفاهم الماثلة مع معهد الشرق الأوسط بالجامعة الأمريكية (طرف ثالث) لتيسير العمل في مثل هذه المبادرات، لدعم تطوير كليات التربية والتطوير المرتكز على المدارس.

وتتلخص أهم الأدوار والمسئوليات لدى أطراف مذكرة التفاهم في البنود الآتية:

البند الرابع

التزامات وزارة التربية والتعليم والتعليم الفني

1. يقوم الطرف الأول باختيار منسق لتيسير الأعمال للمدارس المشاركة في المشروع ويقدم تقريراً شهرياً عن سير العمل لكل من الطرف الثاني والثالث.
2. يقوم الطرف الأول بتقديم التسهيلات للسادة الباحثين من أعضاء هيئة التدريس بالمدارس المشاركة في المشروع.
3. يقوم الطرف الأول باختيار مسنول وحدة التدريب للمدارس المشاركة لتفعيل العمل بالوحدة.
4. يفوض الطرف الأول مدير المدرسة في تنفيذ التوصيات الواردة من الطرف الثاني في إطار مهام الإشراف والمتابعة على المدارس.
5. يفوض الطرف الأول وكيل الوزارة لدعم هذا المشروع ويوفر التسهيلات اللازمة لمدير المدرسة فيما فوض إليه.
6. يقوم الطرف الأول بتيسير وتفعيل وحدات التدريب والجودة داخل المدرسة من خلال عقد ورش عمل دورية ومستمرة وتواصل مستمر مع الجامعة وأعضاء هيئة التدريس.

البند الخامس

التزامات التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي

تبرم الجامعات الحكومية في إطار هذه المذكرة إتفاقيات لاحقاً لتفعيل المبادرة ينص فيها على مراحل تنفيذها و التزامات كل طرف تفصيلياً.

البند السادس

التزامات معهد الشرق الأوسط للتعليم العالي بالجامعة الأمريكية

١. يتولى الطرف الثالث إدارة المشروع.
٢. يتعهد الطرف الثالث بجلب أفضل الخبرات الدولية في هذا المجال.
٣. يقدم الطرف الثالث الدعم الفني للقيام بالدراسات لتحديد إحتياجات المدارس.
٤. ينسق الطرف الثالث الجهود الدولية والوطنية في بناء مواد تدريبية للعاملين بالمدارس الملحقة لتفعيل التنمية المهنية المستدامة.
٥. تؤول هذه المواد في نهاية المشروع إلى الأكاديمية المهنية للمعلمين المعنية بترخيص المعلمين و اعتماد البرامج و التي تتبع الطرف الأول.
٦. يمول الطرف الثالث التجهيزات اللازمة لثلاثة من كليات التربية و لتفعيل وحدات الجودة في إطار ١٥ مدرسة ملحقة دون تحمل أي أعباء مالية على وزارة التربية و التعليم و التعليم الفني ولا على وزارة التعليم العالي و البحث العلمي.

البند السابع

في حالة وجود أي نزاعات بين الأطراف الثلاث يتم حلها بالأساليب الودية.

البند الثامن

مدة تنفيذ الإتفاقية ثلاث سنوات و لا يجوز تجديدها إلا بموافقة الأطراف الثلاث، كذلك لا يجوز تعديل المذكرة إلا بإتفاق الأطراف الثلاث كتابة.

البند التاسع

تدخل هذه المذكرة حيز التنفيذ اعتباراً من تاريخ توقيعها من قبل أطرافها الثلاث.

البند العاشر

إتخذ كل طرف من الأطراف الثلاث من العنوان الموضح بصدر المذكرة محلاً مختاراً له و تعتبر المراسلات على هذا العنوان صحيحة.

البند الحادي عشر

تم التوقيع على هذه المذكرة في مقر ----- بتاريخ ----- من أربع نسخ أصلية باللغة العربية.

معهد الشرق الاوسط للتعليم العالى بالجامعة الأمريكية

ويمثلها

الأستاذ الدكتور إيهاب عبد الرحمن

الرئيس الأكاديمى للجامعة الأمريكية

وزارة التعليم العالى والبحث العلمى

ويمثلها

الأستاذ الدكتور / خالد عبد الغفار

وزير التعليم العالى والبحث العلمى

وزارة التربية والتعليم والتعليم الفنى

ويمثلها

الأستاذ الدكتور طارق شوقى

وزير التربية والتعليم والتعليم الفنى

Memorandum of Understanding

Between The Ministry of Education and Technical Education located at 12 Al Falaki Street, El-Sayeda Zainab, Cairo, Egypt, and represented by The Minister of Education and Technical Education, Prof. Tarek Shawki

And The Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research located at 101 Kasr El Ainy St., Kasr El Ainy, El-Sayeda Zainab, Cairo, Egypt, and represented by The Minister of Higher Education and Scientific Research, Prof. Khalid Atef Abdul Ghaffar

And The Middle East Institute for Higher Education located at The American University in Cairo, Teseen Street, New Cairo, Egypt, and represented by The Provost, Prof. Ehab Abdel-Rahman

Preface:

The Middle East Institute for Higher Education coordinates the project's initiative, which is financed by The European Union ERASMUS+, to develop partnerships between universities and schools that adopt Professional Development schools. The initiative would develop governmental schools as well as faculties of education through building Peer Communities of Learners among them. Similar initiatives in Egypt and developed countries appeared in the previous century and were proven to be successful at adopting and developing schools that were named Professional Development Schools because they led to the professional development of the teachers. Through cooperation and integration between universities and schools, the initiative would guarantee quality within the Faculties of Education and schools and meet the teachers' needs in regards to development and qualifications.

Article One

The previous preface is considered an integral part of the memorandum of understanding and complements its provisions

Article Two

General Objectives

The European Union's project, which is coordinated by The Middle East Institute for Higher Education, aims to append 45 governmental schools with three Faculties of Education from Ain Shams University, Alexandria University and Helwan University with the following criteria:

- Public School
- Neighboring Schools.
- A school with a Quality Assurance Unit
- A school that would be willing to participate in the project
- A school that has a technological infrastructure

As such, the project aims to contribute to the schools and quality assurance units' development with continuous technical support. This initiative is an integral part of the national initiative of developing the faculties of education that is led by the Supreme Council of Universities. Furthermore, the associated schools are an authentic part of the development.

Article Three

Framework of Implementation and Stakeholders

The initiative would be implemented over the period of three years and would start with fifteen schools, five schools for each of the three universities. Afterwards, the schools would form clusters with other neighboring schools to expand and reach a total of forty-five schools at the end of the three years. At the beginning of the project, research to assess the needs of the schools would be performed before giving technical support.

The technical support would be initiated in the first year of the project through action research performed in ARAS, which has activities on educational guidance and the formation of peer communities of learners. These activities were accredited by The Professional Academy for Teachers in 2015. In the following years of the project, the project's team would develop training and coaching material, which will be accredited by the Professional Academy for Teachers and published by the ministry however it should find suitable.

Accordingly and with regards to the importance of the partnership between higher education and pre-university education, consistent communication and integration between the development of both faculties of education and schools would be built on the foundations of research, science and awareness of the focal performance of the teachers. The Ministry of Education and Technical Education (beneficiary 1), and Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (beneficiary 2) agreed to write a memorandum of understanding with Middle East Institute for Higher Education at the American University in Cairo (beneficiary 3) to facilitate the work on the mentioned initiative and to support the development of the faculties of education and the chosen schools.

The roles and commitments of all beneficiaries in the memorandum of understanding are concluded in the following articles:

Article Four

Commitments of The Ministry of Education and Technical Education

1. Beneficiary one would choose a coordinator to facilitate the work with the associated schools and prepare a monthly report on the progress of the work.
2. Beneficiary one would facilitate the work of researchers from faculties of education in the chosen schools.
3. Beneficiary one would choose a representative from the training unit at the chosen schools to mobilize the work at the unit.
4. Beneficiary one would delegate the school principles of the chosen schools to implement the recommendations from other beneficiaries based on the follow-ups and supervisions in the schools.
5. Beneficiary one would delegate the undersecretary of the Ministry of Education to support the project's initiative and provide all the needed facilitation for the principles of the chosen school with authorization.
6. Beneficiary one would facilitate and activate the training and quality units in the schools by holding periodical and ongoing workshops with continuous communication with the universities and faculties of education.

Article Five

Commitments of The Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research

The Governmental Universities would act in the framework of this memorandum of understanding and activate the initiative's objectives according to the stages of the project and detailed responsibilities of beneficiaries.

Article Six

Commitment of The Middle East Institute for Higher Education at the American University

1. Beneficiary three would manage the project.
2. Beneficiary three vows to bring superior international expertise in the field.
3. Beneficiary three would offer technical support in assessing the needs of the schools.
4. Beneficiary three would coordinate national and international efforts to develop educational material for schools to activate Continuing Professional Development.
5. Materials at the end of the project will depart to The Professional Academy for Teachers.
6. Beneficiary three would finance the required preparations for the three faculties of education to activate the quality assurance units at the fifteen schools without bearing any financial burdens on The Ministry of Education and Technical Education or The Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research.

Article Seven

In case of any disputes between the three beneficiaries, friendly resolutions would be used.

Article Eight

The project's term is three years and could not be extended without the three beneficiaries' approval. Furthermore, the memorandum could not be modified without the three beneficiaries' written approval.

Article Nine

This memorandum would come into force after it is signed by the three beneficiaries.

Article Ten

Each of the three beneficiaries have sited their corespondence address in this memorandum.

Article Eleven

This memorandum have been signed at _____ dated _____ from four original copies in Arabic

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The SUP4PCL Partnership: Foundational Principles

The Partnership is about Change and Transformation

The Partnership is a Collaborative and Collegial One

The Partnership Constitutes a Community of Learners

The Partnership is a First Step in Long Lasting Relationships and Friendships

The Partnership Respects Diversity, Multiculturalism and Internationalism

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